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CONTENTS

EDITORIAL	4
Melnyk Yu. B. Message from the Editor-in-Chief of International Journal of Science Annals, Vol. 4, No. 1, 2021	5
SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES	7
Education	
Original Research	
Lhakard P. Motivation and Decision in Choosing Civil Services as a Career of Fourth-Year Students at Chiang Mai University due to the COVID-19 Pandemic	8
Psychology	15
Original Research	
Sabra Z. E. I., Daigham A. I. The Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Training Program on Reducing Emotional and Social Distress: Three Years Follow Up	16
Original Research	
Gordienko-Mytrofanova I. V., Hohol D. M., Nesterenko M. A. Developing the Instructions for the Controlled Association Experiment by Means of Semantic Features for the Stimulus "Flirting Person"	22
Health Care Sciences	33
Original Research	
Chakrabarti S. Psychological Well-Being of COVID Positive Patients During Quarantine in a South Indian Private Hospital	34
LETTERS TO THE EDITOR	42
Letter to the Editor	
Maslov Y. V. A topical methodology research subject in the European area of higher education: ELF, EFL or ESP?	43
Letter to the Editor	
Perasso G. The Play Specialist in the Pediatric Healthcare: Evidence-Based Professionalism, Issues in Practice, and Training Across Different Countries	45

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EDITORIAL

EDITORIAL

EDITORIAL

Message from the Editor-in-Chief
of International Journal of Science Annals,
Vol. 4, No. 1, 2021

Melnyk Yu. B.^{1,2}

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Dear Readers and Authors,

It is a great honor for us to publish the International Journal of Science Annals (IJSA) for the fourth year in a row.

IJSA is an academic periodical peer-reviewed indexed Journal that provides a scientific platform for presenting and discussing new trends and issues in Social and Behavioral Sciences.

IJSA mission: international cooperation of scientists conducting research in the field of integration of human sciences and health.

IJSA Editorial Board includes the most authoritative scientists from 17 countries, 5 continents in the fields of Education, Psychology, Medicine.

For 3.5 years of its existence, the IJSA is presented in more than 35 international scientometric databases, repositories and search engines, such as Crossref System, Google Scholar, OAJI (USA); ISSN, ROAD (France); COPE, EndNote, OpenDOAR, CORE, Jisc (UK); DOAJ, Scilit (Switzerland); Publons (New Zealand); ERIH PLUS, OpenAIRE (Norway); BASE, ResearchGate, ASI (Germany); MIAR (Spain); Index Copernicus International (Poland); DRJI (India); RSCI (Russia); OUCI, National Library of Ukraine (Ukraine), etc.

It is a great honor and responsibility for the IJSA to become a full member of the Committee of Publication Ethics (COPE) (https://is.gd/COPE_IJSA).

The IJSA is indexed in: ICI ICV 91.27; ICDS 3.5; CGI OAJI 0.251

There were some technical changes at the beginning of 2021, of which we would like to inform the Readers and Authors of the IJSA.

Modernization of the IJSA Website

The current development of IT technologies allowed to update the IJSA website (<https://ijsa.culturehealth.org>).

Since 2018, the IJSA has used the “Academic Journal Site Model” developed by me (Melnyk, 2018), which consisted of the following structural elements:

Section 1 “Home” included subsections (<https-pages>): “Journal Info”; “From the Editorial Office”; “Databases, Indexing”;

Section 2 “Editorial Board” included subsections (<https-pages>): “Editorial Board”, “Reviewers”, “Editing and Reviewing Process”.

Section 3 “Editorial Policies” included subsections (<https-pages>): “Editorial Policies”, “Plagiarism Policy”, “Open Access Policy”, “The Ethics Codex of Scientific Publications”, “Disclaimer”, “License Terms”, “Terms of Publications (Fee)”.

Section 4 “Archive” included subsections (<https-pages>): “Previous Issues”, “Current Issue”, “Articles Online First”.

Section 5 “Instructions for Authors” included subsections (<https-pages>): “General Requirements”, “Manuscript Templates”, “Supplemental Materials”.

Section 6 “Statistics” included subsections (<https-pages>): “Publications”, “Authors”, “Readers”.

Section 7 “Contact” included subsections (<https-pages>): “Contact”, “Quick Contact”, “Subscriptions”.

Updated the content of some pages of subsections and documents, among them: Editor and Reviewer Certificates samples, Reviewer Evaluation Form, Template for the Replies to Reviewers’ Comments, etc.

The manuscript templates for all types of publications in the Journal have been updated with detailed instructions for filling out.

For the convenience of Authors in the new interface of the website, the button “Online Submission System” has been added, which allows them to upload manuscripts via the mail server of the website.

The emblems of the Institute, the Publishing and the Repository of the KRPOCH have also been added, which have hyperlinks to relevant websites.

A new position “Keywords Bank” has been created, which makes it possible to quickly search for papers in the Journal by keywords.

In addition, the website is equipped with a search engine for information among all the content of the website.

The website content is presented in English and Ukrainian.

Integration the IJSA Website with the Repository of the KRPOCH Publishing Website

The IJSA website is integrated with the Repository of the KRPOCH Publishing website (<https://ekrpochnet.org/handle/lib/71>) based on the DSpace platform.

This ensured greater integration of the IJSA papers with the global informational scientific space.

The IJSA adheres to the principles of open access and supports a greater global exchange of knowledge. The Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) applies to all papers.

Crossmark Registration has been Introduced for All Papers in the IJSA

A standardized Crossmark button in all IJSA papers allows you to see the status of a content item and look through any additional paper metadata of your choice. The Crossmark button is part of the paper in PDF format, which allows you to inform readers about any changes made to the paper, regardless of the time of its publication on the IJSA website.

Updated Paper Design in the IJSA

The design of title pages of papers has been changed and improved. From now on, the title page of a paper has: the paper title, authors’ names, their institutional belonging and country, the paper history, abstract (structured by the paper elements), Keywords, Copyright, DOI and UDC, information about Conflict of Interests, Peer Review, Source of Support, detailed information about the Authors, and also added Crossmark button.

Each IJSA paper has the Journal’s title in the footers, as well as the volume and issue numbers, print ISSN: 2617-2682; online ISSN: 2707-3637; DOI: 10.26697/ijsa, as well as the logo image of the Journal.

At the end of the paper, there is information on how to cite this paper.

Information about the archives where the paper is available, as well as icons of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) used by the KRPOCH Publishing to publish papers in the IJSA with the appropriate hyperlink to the terms of this license are indicated.

Changes in the Format of Scientific Papers in the IJSA

Due to the new trends, including regarding the references format (APA Style (7th ed.)), the requirements for paper format have been changed.

You can read about the changes both in the online version on the IJSA website and in the printed version at the end of the current issue.

We thank all the Authors and Readers of the IJSA and look forward to further cooperation.

Take care and stay healthy!

References

Melnyk, 2018. Academic Journal Site Model. <https://doi.org/10.26697/Preprint.Melnyk.1.2018>

Dr. Yuriy Melnyk,
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SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES

Education

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Motivation and Decision in Choosing Civil Services as a Career of Fourth-Year Students at Chiang Mai University due to the COVID-19 Pandemic

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The COVID-19 epidemic is affecting the work of people around the world including students who have to graduate and to decide in choosing a civil servant career.

The aim of the study: to explore the motivating factors influencing the decision for the 4th year students of Chiang Mai University to enter the civil service during the COVID era.

Material and Methods:

This study was conducted among fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University. The sample in this study consisted of 362 people. Multiple regression analysis was used to find a linear equation that expressed the relationship between motivating factors and decision-making.

Results:

The findings of this research showed that choosing civil services as a career of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University during the COVID-19 outbreak was high with an average of 3.60. According to hypothesis testing, the factors affecting levels of favorable decision in choosing a civil service career were statistically significant at the 0.05 level in descending order as follows: security, compensation and benefits, values, career path and job characteristics. The influence of personal factors on choosing civil service jobs were not significantly different at the 0.05 level, except the family income factor that influences choosing civil service jobs.

Conclusions:

It was found that personal factors which consisted of gender, domicile, grade point average and average family income per month affecting different government career choices and factors in motivation in deciding to choose a government career containing job characteristics, compensation factor and welfare factors career advancement factors, security factor and value factors had a negative effect on the level of decision-making on the choice of civil service careers.

Keywords:

motivation, civil servant, career choice, Chiang Mai University, COVID-19

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Introduction

When the world is now facing challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic (Hitt et al., 2021; Melnyk, 2020; Zizek, 2020), along with the report from the International Labour Organization (2020), it mentioned that prior to the COVID-19 crisis, there were 178 million young workers employed around the world. Most of them were informal workers whose employment security was not guaranteed if terminated. Four out of ten workers at this age worked in four types of businesses that were mostly affected by the outbreak of COVID-19. Those businesses include wholesale-retail businesses, car and motorcycle repair businesses, factories, real estate and business administration, accommodation and restaurant businesses. The International Labour Organization (2020) calls the new generation who have just graduated and started working during the outbreak of COVID-19, a “lockdown generation”. According to such situation, Thailand, a country with its economic structure relies on industrial and service sectors and overseas exports depending on foreign countries more than 70% (The Secretariat of the House of Representatives, 2018), has its employment rate gradually slowing down. Along with the data from the World Bank (2018) analysing the crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic, the world economy will be heavily affected. The Thai economy recorded the lowest growth in ASEAN and ranked the second from the bottom of the Asia-Pacific region. Besides, the Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council (2020) released a report on Thai society in the first quarter of 2020 indicating that the unemployment rate has been increased to 1.03% with nearly 400,000 unemployed people. It is estimated that this year 8.4 million people will be at risk of being laid off while 520,000 new graduates entering the labour market may be jobless due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Will civil service jobs be another career choice for a new generation in Thailand, especially, for those who are about to graduate or fourth-year students? Civil service jobs have become more popular as observed from the larger number of people taking the civil service competitive examination today. Thus, this research focuses on fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University as these students will graduate and will be in the time of choosing a career after their graduation during the COVID-19 pandemic. They definitely cannot avoid the impact of this pandemic. In addition, Chiang Mai University is a large educational institute in the region and that is why there will be a large number of university graduates entering the labour market in Thailand, and so this is considered a good case study. Hence, the researcher is interested in studying motivation and decision to become a civil servant of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University due to the outbreak of COVID-19.

This paper will help us to understand a new generation, especially those who are about to graduate. What are the factors that they consider in choosing a career and what their motives are? In addition, how important of these factors and motives are in choosing civil service jobs

due to the COVID-19 pandemic? The results of this research would become the data for planning, policy formulation, human resource development in the government sector in the future to achieve operational efficiency to be in accordance with current roles and missions that aim to meet the needs of people and society.

The aim of the study. To explore the motivating factors influencing the decision for the 4th year students of Chiang Mai University to enter the civil service during the COVID era.

Research hypothesis:

1. Personal factors such as gender, domicile, average academic performance levels, and average monthly income of a family differently influence career decision-making on civil service jobs.
2. Motivation factors such as job characteristics, compensation and benefits, career path, job security and values negatively influence the levels of career decision-making on civil service jobs.

Expected benefits of this research:

1. To know what the motivation factors that influence choosing a civil service career of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University during the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. To be used as important and useful information for bureaucracy in planning human resource management system during the COVID-19 pandemic.
3. To make suggestions and guidelines reflected from this research for improvement of bureaucratic model of human resource management in the future.

Materials and Methods

A population and a sample group

The total population of 6,167 fourth-year students were used in this research. The sample size was calculated by using Yamane's formula (1973) and the outcome was a sample of 362 students in total. The Proportional Stratified Random Sampling was also conducted based on 20 faculties where the fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University are studying. Besides, simple random sampling without replacement was used.

Data collection

The researcher collected the data in May 2021 using the questionnaires created which based on related theories, documentation, data and research. The researcher used the questionnaires, which already passed the reliability test to collect data from a sample group. 362 copies of that questionnaire were used and then were given score according to the criteria specified and statistical data was analyzed by using a statistical software.

Data analysis

Once the researcher finished collecting data and checking completeness of the questionnaires, the data was analysed and processed by using a computer and a statistical software. The statistics being used consist of descriptive statistics, which include percentage, mean, standard deviation, and a test statistic that includes t-test, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and multiple regression set at a significance level of 0.05.

Results

According to 362 sets of the questionnaires collected from fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University, the data was analysed in order to prove hypotheses as follows:

- The results of the study on personal factors showed that the majority of a sample group were female accounted for 68.0%. Regarding the total sample, 52.1% of them domiciled in other provinces, 30.6% of them had a cumulative grade point average of 2.25-3.00 and 22.7% of them had a family with monthly income of 20,000 - 30,000 baht.
- The results of the study on job characteristics found that overall, job characteristics was in a high level with an average of 3.44.
- The results of the study on compensation found that overall, compensation was in a high level with an average of 4.15.
- The results of the study on a career path found that overall, a career path was at a moderate level with an average of 2.89.
- The results of the study on a compensation system found that overall, given high compensation system was at a moderate level with an average of 4.2.
- The results of the study on values found that overall, values were at a high level with an average of 3.57.
- The results of the study on choosing civil service jobs found that overall, the students in a sample group decided to choose a civil service career at a high level with an average of 3.60.

Results of hypothesis testing:

1. The hypothesis testing in order to compare decision-making in choosing civil service jobs based on gender. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University with different gender had no different decision-making in choosing civil service jobs, which was not in accordance with the hypothesis created.
2. The hypothesis testing in order to compare decision-making in choosing civil service jobs based on domicile. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University with different domiciles had no different decision-making in choosing civil service jobs, which was not in accordance with the hypothesis created.
3. The hypothesis testing in order to compare decision-making in choosing civil service jobs based on cumulative grade point average. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University with different cumulative grade point average had no different decision-making in choosing civil service jobs, which was not in accordance with the hypothesis created.
4. The hypothesis testing in order to compare decision-making in choosing civil service jobs based on family income. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University with different family income had no different decision-making in choosing civil service jobs, which was not in accordance with the hypothesis created.

5. The hypothesis testing in order to find the relationship between job characteristics and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that job characteristics was related to decision-making in choosing a civil service career of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University significantly at the 0.05 level which was in line with the hypothesis created. In other words, job characteristics positively influence career choice. The better the work system is also the more it is in line with the needs, the more the students will choose civil service jobs.

6. The hypothesis testing in order to find the relationship between compensation system and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that compensation system was related to decision-making in choosing a civil service career of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University and they went in the same direction significantly at the 0.05 level, which was in line with the hypothesis created. In other words, the higher the compensation on both salary and benefits is, the more the students will choose civil service jobs.

7. The hypothesis testing in order to find the relationship between a career path and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that a career path was related to decision-making in choosing a civil service career of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University and they went in the same direction significantly at the 0.05 level, which was in line with the hypothesis created. In other words, the better the career path is, the more the students will choose civil service jobs.

8. The hypothesis testing in order to find the relationship between job security and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that job security was related to decision-making in choosing civil service jobs of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University and they went in the same direction significantly at the 0.05 level, which was in accordance with the hypothesis created. In other words, the more the job security is, the more the students will choose civil service jobs.

9. The hypothesis testing in order to find the relationship between values and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. The result of this hypothesis testing showed that values was related to decision-making in choosing civil service jobs of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University and they went in the same direction significantly at the 0.05 level which was in line with the hypothesis defined. In other words, values positively influence career choice. The more the values are accepted, the more the students will choose civil service jobs.

Discussion

Decision-making towards choosing civil service jobs of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University was in a high level. It showed that a vast majority of the students were more likely to decide to enter a government job because of the COVID-19 pandemic. This was due to

job security, a lifetime employment as well as compensation on both salaries and benefits that are more developed to be equivalent to that of the private sector. In addition, values started to change according to the COVID-19 pandemic. Civil service jobs are seen as a career option, which is not affected by the pandemic, and have a long-term security. This is consistent with the research conducted by Deal, Altman, and Rogelberg (2010). The research found that people who decided to choose jobs in civil services place importance on security and benefits as incentive due to more need for security in life.

Gender. According to the hypothesis testing on gender and choosing civil services as a career, this was done by finding the difference between the mean of two independent sample groups called the Independent-Sample T-Test. The Sig. value of 0.075 was obtained which was greater than a significance level of 0.05. Thus, the findings revealed that male and female students' motivation on choosing civil service jobs was not significantly different at the 0.05 level. This is because today the opening of competitive examinations and positions gives equality in employee recruitment for both male and female candidates to be selected. In addition, both of them give priority to wages and career path with no difference, enabling both genders choose a career that promotes salary and career path. Consequently, the gender factor did not influence the degree of career decision-making towards civil service jobs. Such result was in accord with the research conducted by Amornwongpaiboon and Arsuwattanakul (2018), stating that different genders had no influence on the motivation of career choice in choosing a civil service job.

Domicile. There was no different decision-making in choosing civil service jobs among fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University who come from different provinces, including from the north, northeast, south, central and east of the country, and the students in Bangkok. According to the hypothesis testing on domicile and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted, and the Sig. value of 0.086 was obtained which was greater than a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the findings indicated that different domiciles did not affect the students' decision in choosing civil service jobs significantly differently at the 0.05 level. This is consistent with others research, which studied the relationship between personal variables and motivating

factors in career selection among new graduates of Universities. Research found that students from different domiciles overall had no different motivating factors in choosing a career. The reason for the aforementioned research results was that a civil service job is related to the public care service, so the regulations from the Office of the Civil Service Commission (2021) provides equal acceptance regulations for all individuals who will serve in the civil service equally in different areas.

Academic performance. According to the hypothesis testing on average academic performance levels and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted and the Sig. value of 0.065 was obtained which was greater than a significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was concluded that different average academic performance levels did not affect the students' decision in choosing civil service jobs significantly differently at the 0.05 level. In other words, different academic performance was not a factor that led students choose a civil service career differently. This is in line with the research conducted by Amornwongpaiboon and Arsuwattanakul (2018). They found that different academic performance had no influence on motives for choosing a civil service career because the Civil Service Commission does not specify any condition on academic performance recruitment for civil service jobs.

As to the hypothesis testing on average monthly income of a family and choosing civil services as a career, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted, and the Sig. value of 0.028 was obtained which was less than a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, it was concluded that different average family income affected the students' decision in choosing civil service jobs significantly differently at the 0.05 level. This is in accordance with Hauw and Vos (2010). They found that different family income had given different opinions towards civil service jobs because during the outbreak of COVID-19, family income was decreased. This happened especially with the families whose income was from merchant jobs or the families that did not work in civil services. This resulted in lower income, which affected income security, so the students foresee this long-term income security in civil service jobs.

The results of the analysis on personal factors and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Analysis on Personal Factors and Decision-Making in Choosing Civil Service Jobs of Fourth-Year Students at Chiang Mai University

Independent variables	p-value	Test results	
		Accept	Reject
Gender	0.075	+	-
Domicile	0.086	+	-
Level of education	0.065	+	-
Family income	0.028	-	+

In terms of job security, it is a factor in attraction that influences decision-making in choosing civil service jobs at a significance level of 0.05, which most demonstrates the relationship between the two variables in the same direction. According to the result of this research, it was found that the T-Test statistic had a Sig. value of 0.00, which was less than a significance level of 0.05, thus the hypothesis was accepted. This could be interpreted that the job security factor positively affects decision-making towards civil service jobs. It showed the students' ideas towards those jobs. They thought that this type of job was a stable job, especially, in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic; therefore, job security was a factor that should be considered when choosing a career in the long term. This is in line with the research conducted by Srinivasan (2012). The research states that having a stable job is the most important factor when considering making career decisions due to a prominent feature of civil service jobs as lifetime employment. An employee simply cannot be fired unless his or her actions constitute serious misconduct. In addition, a civil service job is a job that guarantees monthly salary from a government budget. A salary received from working as a civil servant is consistent and stable. This is because working in the civil service receives a permanent salary from a government, which is more stable and secure than from the private sector, and a payroll by a government is more certain than that of the private one as it has been fixed according to payments scheduled.

Regarding compensation, it was found that there was the relationship between compensation and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs at a significance level of 0.05 and the relationship was correlated in the same direction. According to the result of this research, it was found that the T-Test statistic had a Sig. value of 0.000, which was less than a significance level of 0.05. This could be interpreted that the compensation factor including benefits influences decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. That is in line with the research conducted by Amornwongpaiboon and Arsuwattanakul (2018). The research states that compensation and benefits is the factor that influences career choice. As for the compensation system, it shows that the higher the compensation is, the more the students will choose civil service jobs. The government sector has adjusted the minimum salary to compete with the private sector. In addition, as to such COVID-19 pandemic, income and the economy of Thailand have been greatly affected (The Bank of Thailand, 2020). Particularly, the private sector has to undertake salary cuts or to maintain employee retention but without pay. While on the other hand government agencies still pay their employees' salaries and benefits regularly. Most of the students see that benefits received from working in civil services such as medical expenses, children's tuition fees, pensions are worth working for the government sector. Hence, this is one of the reasons why fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University more consider on this factor.

As for values, they were found to be correlated with decision-making in choosing civil service jobs at a

significance level of 0.05, and their relationship was correlated in the same direction. The hypothesis was secondarily accepted. This showed that values influence decision-making in choosing a civil service career. According to the result of this research, it was found that the T-Test statistic had a Sig. value of 0.000, which was less than a significance level of 0.05, thus the hypothesis was accepted. This could be interpreted that values have a positive influence on choosing civil service jobs. In studying the work motivation (Ford, 1992) and comparing employees' work motivation based on Alderfer's ERG theory in three areas: existence, relatedness and growth (Alderfer, 1969), values were found at a moderate level. Looking at the COVID-19 pandemic, young people who graduate want to be entrepreneurs, or simply be their own boss. This could lead to changing values and even more tendency in the future, if the COVID-19 pandemic continues in the future. The students' values in choosing a career may tend to change more.

As for career path, the result of this study showed that there was the relationship between career path and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs at a significance level of 0.05, and their relationship was correlated in the same direction. The hypothesis was thirdly accepted. According to the result of this research, it was found that the T-Test statistic had a Sig. value of 0.021, which was less than a significance level of 0.05, thus the hypothesis was accepted. This could be interpreted that career path influences decision-making in choosing civil service jobs. Since bureaucracy has official structure on promotion plans in each position and each department, allowing people who make career decisions know their own career path. This is in accordance with Haar et al. (2014). It is the study about the relationship among motivation, leadership and organizational climate. The study revealed that career path influenced work.

The other study (Alniacik et al., 2012) examines the relationships between the components of career motivation, employees' affective commitment and their job satisfaction, while controlling their demographic characteristics such as age, gender, income and organizational tenure. For this aim, it was conducted a field research on employees working in various industries. Research results (Alniacik et al., 2012) showed that career motivation has a positive correlation with organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Individual characteristics except respondents' gender did not exert any significant association with career motivation.

However, career path under the civil service system when compared to the private sector's still takes more steps and more time to move up to a higher position than the private sector.

As for job characteristics, it was found that there was the relationship between job characteristics and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs at a significance level of 0.05, and their relationship was correlated in the same direction. The hypothesis was least accepted. According to the result of this research, the finding was

that the T-Test statistic had a Sig. value of 0.003, which was less than a significance level of 0.05, thus the hypothesis was accepted. This could be interpreted that job characteristics positively influence decision-making towards choosing civil service jobs. Bureaucracy has its job/work design in accordance with its work system, which allows individuals to choose to work according to their interests. There are also projects that provide opportunities to challenge themselves and have the authority to take responsibility at work. This is in line with Jauhar, Chan and Rahim (2017). This researcher studied behaviour of the Generation Y at workplace that

affects works in an organization. Generation Y employees prefer working with people and working with freedom of thoughts. Nonetheless, in practice, there may be some departments that are still inflexible and undertake a defensive approach rather than proactive approach at work. Therefore, the image of job characteristics of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University is still low when compared to other pull factors.

Forecasting equations for the relationship between motivation factors in choosing civil service jobs are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Forecasting Equations for the Relationship between Motivation Factors in Choosing Civil Service Jobs

Variables	Coefficients				
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	5.764	2.268	-	2.055	0.034
Job characteristics	0.304	0.089	0.233	2.305	0.003
Compensation	0.685	0.160	0.339	5.384	0.000
Career path	0.308	0.189	0.178	2.329	0.021
Job security	0.689	0.133	0.295	5.984	0.000
Values	0.535	0.149	0.236	4.267	0.000

Note. *B* – the unstandardized beta; *SE B* – the standard error for the unstandardized beta; β – the standardized beta; *t* – the T-test statistic; *p* – the probability value.

Conclusions

According to the study of motivation and decision-making in choosing civil service jobs of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University during the COVID-19 pandemic, the researcher would like to present the ideas and conclusions that may be helpful to the development of bureaucracy to attract students. Proactive policies should be designed to attract individuals who are ready and competent to choose civil service jobs.

The ideas and conclusions are presented as follows:

- 1) The research found that decision-making in choosing civil service jobs of fourth-year students at Chiang Mai University was in a high level. This means that bureaucracy still motivates students to choose working in civil services due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This is another important opportunity for the government sector to select high potential employees to enter civil services. For example, the government can develop proactive policies to motivate these students to work in civil services more because this will help the government to receive modern employees to help develop new projects, new policies that respond to the needs of the country. Besides, they will become an essential workforce in driving government policies in the age of rapidly changing under globalization in order to most efficiently meet the needs of people.
- 2) With policies to attract high-potential employees, the bureaucracy itself should be designed with work systems and job characteristics that are flexible, wide open, and given the opportunity to move up in a higher position equally with that of the private sector. Initially, these

students might not be interested in civil service jobs, but after the COVID-19 pandemic, the students have become more interested in and decided to work in the civil service. Therefore, the more the modern design of job characteristics that meets the needs, way of life and thoughts of a new generation is carried out, the more it will attract young employees with high competence to work for the government sector. This will also help keep them working in the government sector and not leaving to work in the private sector and will become important workforce for the development of the country.

Suggestions for future research:

- There should be a wider range of research which can be done by conducting research with university students in the public universities in different regions or at overall level of the country regarding how career decision of entering civil services has been made after the COVID-19 pandemic as well as whether students make the same or different decisions.
- This research can be further expanded through studying on trends of career choice of students in the post-COVID-19 era.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee.

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References

- Alderfer, C. P. (1969). An empirical test of a new theory of human needs. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 4(2), 142–175. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(69\)90004-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(69)90004-X)
- Alniacik, U., Alniacik, E., Akcin K., & Erat, S. (2012). Relationships between career motivation, affective commitment and job satisfaction. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 355–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.1011>
- Amornwongpaiboon, C., & Arsuwattanukul, C. (2018). The decision making to work in the civil service career of senior students, Kasetsart University, Bangkok Campus. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Research: Graduate Studies*, 7(1), 178–187. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3245057>
- Banchanont, P. (2017, January 6). *Analysis of Thailand 4.0: National vision that still lack details*. BBC. <http://www.bbc.com/thai/thailand-38527250>
- Deal, J., Altman, D., & Rogelberg, S. (2010). Millennials at work: What we know and what we need to do (if anything). *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 25(2), 191–199. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-010-9177-2>
- Ford, M. E. (1992). *Motivating humans: Goals, emotions, and personal agency beliefs*. SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483325361>
- Haar, J., Russo, M., Suñe, A., & Ollier-Malaterre, A. (2014). Outcomes of work-life balance on job satisfaction, life satisfaction and mental health: A study across seven cultures. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 85(3), 361–373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2014.08.010>
- Hauw, S., & Vos, A. (2010). Millennials' career perspective and psychological contract expectations: Does the recession lead to lowered expectations? *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 25(2), 293–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-010-9162-9>
- Hitt, M. A., Holmes, R. M., & Arreglec, J.-L. (2021). The (COVID-19) pandemic and the new world (dis)order. *Journal of World Business*, 56(4), 101210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2021.101210>
- Jauhar, J., Ting, Ch. S., & Rahim, N. F. (2017). The impact of reward and transformational leadership on the intention to quit of Generation Y employees in oil and gas industry: Moderating role of job satisfaction. *Global Business and Management Research*, 9(4), 426–441.
- Melnyk, Yu. B. (2020). International view at health: World after pandemic COVID-19. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 3(2), 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijsa.2020.2.4>
- Srinivasan, V. (2012). Multi generations in the workforce: Building collaboration. *IIMB Management Review*, 24(1), 48–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2012.01.004>
- The Bank of Thailand. (2020). *Report on the situation of the COVID-19 virus affecting financial markets*. https://www.bot.or.th/Thai/BOTMagazine/Pages/256305TheKnowledge_DebtMeasure.aspx#
- The International Labour Organization. (2020, April 29). *ILO Monitor: COVID-19 and the world of work. Third edition. Updated estimates and analysis*. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/@dgreports/@dcomm/documents/briefingnote/wcms_743146.pdf
- The Office of the Civil Service Commission. (2021). *Roles and responsibilities of OCSC*. <https://www.ocsc.go.th/english/ocsc>
- The National Economic and Social Development Council (2020). *Economic Outlook*. https://www.nesdc.go.th/main.php?filename=Q_GDP_report
- The Secretariat of the House of Representatives, (2018). *Report on Reform of the Government Compensation System and Benefits*. https://www.parliament.go.th/ewtadmin/ewt/parliament_parc-y/ewt_dl_link.php?nid=52029&filename=index
- The World Bank. (2018). *Doing business 2019: Training for reform*. World Bank Publications. <https://www.doingbusiness.org/en/reports/global-reports/doing-business-2019>
- Yamane, T. (1973). *Statistics: An introductory analysis* (3rd ed.). Harper & Row.
- Zizek, S. (2020). *Pandemic!: COVID-19 shakes world*. John Wiley & Sons.

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**SOCIAL AND
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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Training Program on Reducing Emotional and Social Distress: Three Years Follow Up

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

This paper addresses the question: is a brief cognitive behavior therapy training program enhances psychologist's skills as reflected in scores on cognitive therapy skills scale and in helping students with emotional and social problems?

The aim of the study: to explore the impact of the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy training program on reducing emotional and social distress over 3 years.

Material and Methods:

Participants are 35 school psychologists (20 females and 15 males) have received intensive cognitive behavior therapy training for 6 days during two weeks followed by one to one supervision in school sittings for three months. Participants completed cognitive behavior therapy scale. Individual and group counseling sessions delivered to male and female (age mean is 13.7 years) students known of emotional and social problems during the current school year. Supervisors wrote a report in the end of three months practice, students and parent's feedback had collected.

Results:

Results show that differences between pre and post scores on cognitive behavior therapy scale are statistically significant ($t=4.92$), supervisors reports and students feedback indicate improving therapeutic skills by the end of three months practice.

Conclusions:

Cognitive behavior therapy training program has positive influence in enhancing cognitive behavior therapy skills in school psychologists that reflected in providing effective counseling for students with emotional and social problems. Supervision based training optimizing the therapeutic outcome in both individual and group therapy sessions. Follow up of 3 years revealed continuous effect of the training and continuous supervision in improving counseling skills of school psychologists.

Keywords:

cognitive behavior therapy, emotional problems, social problems, cognitive behavior therapy skills, cognitive therapy scale

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Introduction

Psychological services in the governmental schools face many challenges, since it established in 1990 side to side with the social services (Abousrea et al., 2009; Sherefeen & Abouhasona, 2011). School psychologist's jobs were limited to behavioral assessment of emotional and academic problems (Ismael, 2006). School psychologists are willing to offer better job by applying the counseling and therapeutic change with students who suffered because of emotional, interpersonal, or academic problems (Yousef, 2009). One of the barriers to achieve this goal is preparing the school psychologists to be competent in delivering a professional help with these problems (Albana, 1990; Elfeky, 1990; Ismael, 2006; Kamel, 1990; Taha, 1990; Yousef, 2009).

Psychotherapeutic competence is conceptualized as a therapist's general and treatment-specific knowledge level, skill level, and values or attitudes while implementing therapeutic interventions (Kühne et al., 2020). Assessment of psychotherapeutic competences are essential to training, supervision, clients care, quality control, and life-long practice (Kühne et al., 2019). Assessment of therapeutic competence may provide therapists with formative and summative feedback and may guide self-reflection (Muse & McManus, 2013).

Cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) have been consistently shown to be effective across a wide range of disorders (Ho et al., 2016; Hofmann et al., 2012; Kobori et al., 2014). Previous CBT training evaluations indicate that trainees' clinical competence and knowledge improve over the training period (McManus et al., 2010). Measurement of cognitive behavioral therapy competency is designed to reveal how well therapists deliver CBT, the results of which can serve many important functions in research and clinical training contexts and has the potential to optimize training and dissemination of CBT (Rozek et al., 2018). Cognitive Therapy Scale developed by Young and Beck in 1980 for assessing CBT skills (Young & Beck, 1980a; 1980b). It is the most established measurement of therapist competence in the context of providing CBT (Weck et al., 2016).

This study is interested in investigating how far brief cognitive therapy training could enhance school psychologists CBT skills and offer better help for students known with emotional and social problems.

School psychologists are capable to help students with their psychological problems, as they spend relatively long time with them and know about their strengths and weaknesses as well.

Adjustment in school environment is very important and has a great impact on student's overall adjustment and psychological health.

For the study of psycho-adaptive and psychomaladaptive personality disorders, complexes of psychological and medical methods for diagnosing mental health are mainly used, which allows revealing psychological peculiarities of the subjects (Melnyk & Stadnik, 2018).

Cognitive behavior therapy is known as an effective treatment for many of the psychological problems

(Beck, 1967; 1976; 1991; 1993; 1995; 1997; 2005; Beck et al., 1979; 2004; Clark et al., 1999), but results depend on the therapists' skill and competences (Kazantzis et al., 2018). Training could enhance cognitive behavior therapy skills and enable those psychologists to help students to cope with their emotional and interpersonal problems. Supervision is essential in learning cognitive behavior therapy. Despite the divergence in systems of psychotherapy, their goals and varied training practices, supervision remains the one component considered essential to all (O'Donovan et al., 2011). Miller's hierarchical framework for assessing clinical skill, ranging from therapists' knowledge of CBT ("knows"), their practical understanding ("knows how"), their skill within artificial clinical simulations ("shows how"), and their skill within real clinical practice settings ("does") (Muse et al., 2017). In his definition of supervision Milne (2009) stated that the formal provision, by approved supervisors, of a relationship-based education and training that is work-focused and which manages, supports, develops and evaluates the work of colleague/s (precision). It therefore differs from related activities, such as mentoring and therapy, by incorporating an evaluative component (precision by differentiation) and by being obligatory. The main methods that supervisors use is corrective feedback on the supervisees' performance, teaching, and collaborative goal-setting (specification). The objectives of supervision are "normative" (e. g. case management and quality control issues), "restorative" (e. g. encouraging emotional experiencing and processing) and "formative" (e. g. maintaining and facilitating the supervisees' competence (Milne, 2009).

There is a growing body of literature showing that therapists receiving supervision have more positive clients' outcomes in therapy (O'Donovan et al., 2011). The importance of this study in one aspect is that, helping the psychologists to enhance their professional skills in counseling and therapy services. On other aspects it enables testing the actual results of the training in real life sittings within schools. By giving them the opportunities to refine their counseling skills under a close extended supervision and evaluation of client's outcome from various perspectives.

Few studies have examined multiple perspectives (i. e. independent observer, supervisor, trainee therapists and patient) of competency evaluation and few studies have examined all perspectives together (Rozek et al., 2018). Current study collects data from supervisors, students, teachers and parents, which enables considering multiple feedback of therapy outcome.

The aim of the study. To explore the impact of the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy training program on reducing emotional and social distress over three years.

Materials and Methods

Participants and Supervisors

School psychologists of total number 35 (20 females and 15 males) with mean age of 31.7 years, average of 5.4 years of experience. Table 1 shows participants' characteristics.

Table 1

Participants Demographic Data

Characteristics	Value
Total participants	35
Participants by gender ratio	15 males 20 females
Age mean	31.7
Experience years mean	5.4
Qualifications:	
- Bachelor's degree	31
- Master's degree	2
- PhD degree	2

Two Supervisors participated in the current study is a Clinical Psychologists (trained in CBT). Supervisor has served as trainers in psychotherapy training for 7, and 17 years. Supervisor (1) had 12 years of clinical experience and school counseling. He got his PhD degree in Counseling and Psychological Wellbeing. Supervisor (2) had 23 years of clinical experience and academic teaching of Clinical Psychology.

The study used the following scales: the Cognitive Therapy Scale and the Cognitive Behavior Therapy Skills Scale.

The Cognitive Therapy Scale (CTS) was developed by Young and Beck (1980), and modified by Blackburn and colleagues (Blackburn et al., 2001; James et al., 2001). An Egyptian version of the CTS validated by Sabra (2017); Sabra and Daigham (2020), contains 11 items that evaluate specific aspects of therapist competence including agenda setting, dealing with problems/questions/objections, clarity of communication, pacing and efficient use of time, interpersonal effectiveness, resource activation, reviewing previously set homework, using feedback and summaries, guided discovery, focusing on central cognitions and behaviors, rationale, selecting appropriate strategies, appropriate implementation of techniques and assigning homework.

The CTS uses a 7-point rating scale format: 0 = poor, 1= barely adequate, 2= mediocre, 3= satisfactory, 4= good, 5= very good, and 6 = excellent.

In the current study, the inter-rater reliability of the CTS mean scores between the two raters was high (0.87).

The Cognitive Behavior Therapy Skills Scale (CBTS) consists of 40 items with 5 points Likert rating scale of 1= not use it at all to 5= use it most of the times. Alpha reliability is 0.92 (n=55) and test retest reliability is 0.74 (n= 20) with good validity indicators (Sabra, 2017).

Students' feedback after each session and behavioral observation of class mates included in sessions report that reviewed by supervisors.

Supervision is an educational process and, as such, benefits from using well-established principles that are known (from other contexts) to improve the likelihood of learning (Pilling & Roth, 2014, p. 26):

1. Written reports of psychological counseling sessions as a part of psychological activity plans during school

year. The reports include activity plan, intervention tools and evaluation notes.

2. Supervisors tasks is to help implementing and to evaluate the following items:

- agenda setting: suitable items, feasible agenda;
- CBT interventions: appropriate intervention targets, choosing suitable interventions, rationale for interventions, implementing interventions;
- homework: choosing suitable homework, reviewing homework, rationale for homework, planning homework;
- assessing change: choosing suitable measures;
- effective two-way communication: empathic understanding, collaboration, client feedback, reflective summaries.

Procedures

Participants attend 6 days training in cognitive behavior therapy. The training included basics and techniques of cognitive behavior therapy of Adolescents problems. Participants completed Cognitive Behavior Therapy Skills Scale before and after the training course.

A close supervision is established for the first stage implementation in eleven preparatory schools. General psycho educational plan for students of these schools have been set, and individual counseling for students with emotional and interpersonal problems conducted too.

Feedback from students who received individual and group CBT counseling sessions for emotional and interpersonal problems collected. Other teachers and parent's feedback about those students' behaviors collected too. Supervisors reports collected by the end of each 3 months.

Follow up during 36 months to evaluate and enhance the counseling service in the Beni Mazar district primary schools.

Results and Discussion

CBT training program has positive influence in enhancing CBT skills in school psychologists that reflected:

1. Results of t-test of paired samples, of CBTSS scores show that there are significant differences between pre and post mean scores as shown in Table 2-3.

Table 2
 Paired Sample Statistics

CBTSS	<i>M</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SEM</i>
CBTSS post	168.85	33	27.373	5.211
CBTSS pre	157.76	33	29.933	4.765

Note. CBTSS post – scores on cognitive behavioral therapy skills scale after training; CBTSS pre – scores on cognitive behavioral therapy skills scale before training; *M* – the mean (average); *N* – participants; *SD* – the standard deviation; *SEM* – the standard error of the mean.

Table 3
 Results of Paired Sample T-Test (*N*=33)

CBTSS	Paired differences			<i>T</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SEM</i>			
Pair 1, CBTSS post & CBTSS pre	11.091	12.93	2.251	4.927	32	0.000

Note. CBTSS post – scores on cognitive behavioral therapy skills scale after training; CBTSS pre – scores on cognitive behavioral therapy skills scale before training; *M* – the mean (average); *SD* – the standard deviation; *SEM* – the standard error of the mean; *T* – the t-test statistic; *DF* – the degrees of freedom; *Sig.* – significance level.

2. Providing effective counseling for students with emotional and interpersonal problems as indicated of reporting that:

- reduced complaints of student's problematic behaviors;
- increasing involvement in counseling activities and sessions;
- parents reports show that kids became able to listen and conduct calmer communication between each other's;
- kids became more comfortable communicating with teachers and adults in their social network;
- kids are more motivated to participate in school activities and more likely to follow school rules.

3. Supervision helped in optimizing the therapeutic outcome in both individual and group therapy sessions:

- after 3 years of follow up, supervisor report shows that, psychological counseling became an established process in school year activity plan;
- more schools became included in CBT counseling systematically. Psychologists became more familiar with CBT structure and use it in their routine counseling work with students.

4. Efforts to communicate with students and their families during pandemic are continuing to help students cope with educational and evaluation method change since March 2020.

5. Psychologists participated in enhancing awareness and protection of COVID-19 for students and their families.

6. Psychologists provide brief useful psych education on anxiety symptoms that are widely spread during pandemic time through telehealth techniques.

7. In the beginning of the 2018-2019 school year total of 105 school psychologist finished the cognitive behavior therapy training and were ready to establish the cognitive therapy and positive thinking program in all preparatory schools in Beni Mazar district.

8. The cognitive therapy and positive thinking program considered as a standard psychological activity programme to be repeated each semester during the time between September 2018–March 2020.

Conclusions

Cognitive behavior therapy training program has positive influence in enhancing cognitive behavior therapy skills in school psychologists that reflected in providing effective counseling for students with emotional and social problems. Supervision based training optimizing the therapeutic outcome in both individual and group therapy sessions. Follow up of 3 years revealed continuous effect of the training and continuous supervision in improving counseling skills of school psychologists.

Research limitations and recommendations for future studies:

- Data collection in this research focused on client outcome and supervisors' reports. Need for collecting data on supervisees' competence, that include supervisors systematically sampling supervisees' in-session behaviour as O'Donovan and colleagues (O'Donovan et al., 2011) recommended.
- Future research should continue to work on validating and refining competency measures in order to enhance training and, allowing for better clients' outcomes.
- Future studies needed to replicate these findings with a larger sample and a wider variety of counselor's experience.
- More tools are needed to improve tele-counseling processes.

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Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee.

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References

- Abousrea, O., Shawky, M., Anwar, A., & Ismael, S. (2009). Life skills program for enriching the scholastic environment. Guide for senior school psychologists. *Research and Studies in Psychology* (pp. 311–350). Cairo University, Faculty of Arts press.
- Albana, K. (1990). *Therapeutic duties of psychologists in Egypt* [Paper presentation]. Forum for Scientific and Practical Preparing Psychologists in Egypt, Technological Development and Planning Institute, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.
- Beck, A. (1967). *Depression: Clinical, experimental, and theoretical aspects*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Beck, A. T., Baruch, E., Balter, J. M., Steer, R. A., & Warman, D. M. (2004). A new instrument for measuring insight: The beck cognitive insight scale. *Schizophrenia Research*, 68(2), 319–329. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-9964\(03\)00189-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-9964(03)00189-0)
- Beck, A. T. (1976). *Cognitive therapy and the emotional disorders*. A Meridian Book.
- Beck, A. T. (1991). Cognitive therapy: A 30-year retrospective. *American Psychologist*, 46(4), 368–375. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.46.4.368>
- Beck, A. T. (1993). Cognitive therapy: Past, present, and future. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 61(2), 194–198. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006X.61.2.194>
- Beck, A. T., Rush, A. J., Shaw, B. F., & Emery, G. (1979). *Cognitive therapy of depression*. Guilford Press.
- Beck, A. T. (2005). The current state of cognitive therapy: A 40-year retrospective. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 62(9), 953–959. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.62.9.953>
- Beck, A. T. (1997). The past and future of cognitive therapy. *The Journal of Psychotherapy Practice and Research*, 6(4), 276–284.
- Beck, J. S. (1995). *Cognitive therapy: Basics and beyond*. Guilford Press.
- Blackburn, I. M., James, I. A., Milne, D. L., Baker, C., Standart, S., Garland, A., & Reichelt, F. K. (2001). The revised cognitive therapy scale (CTS-R): Psychometric properties. *Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy*, 29(4), 431–446. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1352465801004040>
- Clark, D. A., Beck, A. T., & Alford, B. A. (1999). *Scientific foundations of cognitive theory and therapy*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Elfeky, I. (1990). *Roles of the school psychologist* [Paper presentation]. Forum for Scientific and Practical Preparing Psychologists in Egypt, Technological Development and Planning Institute, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.
- Ho, F. Y., Chan, C. S., & Tang, K. N. (2016). Cognitive-behavioral therapy for sleep disturbances in treating posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 43, 90–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2015.09.005>
- Hofmann, S. G., Asnaani, A., Vonk, I. J. J., Sawyer, A. T., & Fang, A. (2012). The efficacy of cognitive behavioral therapy: A review of meta-analyses. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 36, 427–440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-012-9476-1>
- Ibrahim, Z. E. (2019). Teachers attitudes toward special need students and teaching sittings readiness in Egypt. *International Journal of Education and Science*, 2(2), 45. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijes.2019.2.31>
- Ismael, S. (2006). *Obstacles that face profession of psychology in Egypt*. Annual book of Faculty of Arts-Cairo University. Cairo University Press.
- James, I. A., Blackburn, I. M., & Reichelt, F. K. (2001). *Manual of the revised cognitive therapy scale (CTS-R)*. Newcastle Cognitive and Behavioural Therapies Centre, Newcastle. <https://www.ed.ac.uk/files/atoms/files/ctsmanual1.pdf>
- Kamel, A. (1990). *Academic and occupational foundations for preparing psychologists* [Paper presentation]. Forum for Scientific and Practical Preparing Psychologists in Egypt, Technological Development and Planning Institute, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.
- Kazantzis, N., Clayton, X., Cronin, T. J., Farchione, D., Limburg, K., & Dobson, K. S. (2018). The cognitive therapy scale and cognitive therapy scale-revised as measures of therapist competence in cognitive behavior therapy for depression: Relations with short and long term outcome. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 42(4), 385–397. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-018-9919-4>
- Kobori, O., Nakazato, M., Yoshinaga, N., Shiraishi, T., Takaoka, K., Nakagawa, A., Iyo, M., & Shimizu, E. (2014). Transporting Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and the Improving Access to Psychological Therapies (IAPT) project to Japan: Preliminary observations and service evaluation in Chiba. *The Journal of Mental Health Training, Education and Practice*, 9(3), 155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMHTEP-10-2013-0033>
- Kühne, F., Lacki, F. J., Muse, K., & Weck, F. (2019). Strengthening competence of therapists-in-training in the treatment of health anxiety (hypochondriasis): Validation of the Assessment of Core CBT Skills (ACCS). *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 26(3), 319–327. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpp.2353>
- Kühne, F., Meister, R., Maaß, U., Paunov, T., & Weck, F. (2020). How reliable are therapeutic

- competence ratings? Results of a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 44(2), 241–257. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-019-10056-5>
- McManus, F., Westbrook, D., Vazquez-Montes, M., Fennell, M., & Kennerley, H. (2010). An evaluation of the effectiveness of Diploma-level training in cognitive behaviour therapy. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 48(11), 1123–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2010.08.002>
- Melnyk, Yu., & Stadnik, A. (2018). Mental health of a personality: Diagnostics and prevention of mental disorders. *International Journal of Education and Science*, 1(3-4), 50. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijes.2018.3-4.37>
- Milne, D. (2009). *Evidence-based clinical supervision: Principles and practice*. BPS Blackwell. <https://download.e-bookshelf.de/download/0000/5989/37/L-G-0000598937-0015302470.pdf>
- Muse, K., & McManus, F. (2013). A systematic review of methods for assessing competence in cognitive-behavioural therapy. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 33(3), 484–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2013.01.010>
- Muse, K., McManus, F., Rakovshik, S., & Thwaites, R. (2017). Development and psychometric evaluation of the Assessment of Core CBT Skills (ACCS): An observation-based tool for assessing cognitive behavioral therapy competence. *Psychological Assessment*, 29(5), 542–555. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pas0000372>
- O'Donovan, A., Halford, W. K., & Walters, B. (2011). Towards best practice supervision of clinical psychology trainees. *Australian Psychologist*, 46(2), 101–112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-9544.2011.00033.x>
- Pilling, S., & Roth, A. D. (2014). The competent clinical supervisor. In C. E. Watkins Jr. & D. L. Milne (Eds.), *The Wiley international handbook of clinical supervision* (pp. 20–37). John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118846360.ch2>
- Rozek, D. C., Serrano, J. L., Marriott, B. R., Scott, K. S., Hickman, L. B., Brothers, B. M., Levis, C. C., & Simons, A. D. (2018). Cognitive behavioural therapy competency: Pilot data from a comparison of multiple perspectives. *Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy*, 46(2), 244–250. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1352465817000662>
- Sabra, Z. I. (2017). Cognitive behavioral therapy skills in profession and daily life contexts. *Psychological Studies*, 38(1), 25–93.
- Sabra, Z. E. I., & Daigham, A. I. (2020). Therapeutic competencies in reducing emotional and social distress after cognitive behavior therapy training program. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 3(1), 55–56. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijisa.2020.1.7>
- Sherefeen, A., & Abouhasana, N. (2011). Factors that predict professional motivation in counseling Psychology' students at Jordanian Universities. *Faculty of Education Journal*, 35(1), 127–164.
- Taha, F. (1990). *Toward an impetuous academic program for preparing psychologists in Egyptian Universities* [Paper presentation]. Forum for Scientific and Practical Preparing Psychologists in Egypt, Technological Development and Planning Institute, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.
- Weck, F., Jakob, M., Neng, J. M., Höfling, V., Grikscheit, F., & Bohus, M. (2016). The effects of bug-in-the-eye supervision on therapeutic alliance and therapist competence in cognitive-behavioural therapy: A randomized controlled trial. *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 23(5), 386–396. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpp.1968>
- Young, J., & Beck, A. (1980). *Cognitive therapy scale (CTS)* [Database record]. APA PsycTests. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t00834-000>
- Young, J., & Beck, A. T. (1980). *Cognitive therapy scale rating manual*. https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.academyofct.org/resource/collection/24743CF7-351E-4335-9E93-83F26EF675A3/CTRS_Manual.pdf
- Yousef, G. S. (2009). Contributions of psychologists in practice of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (exploratory study). *Research and Studies in Psychology* (pp. 27–49). Cairo University, Faculty of Arts press.

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SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Psychology

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Developing the Instructions for the Controlled Association Experiment by Means of Semantic Features for the Stimulus “Flirting Person”

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

This article continues a series of studies devoted to ludic competence/playfulness and one of its components is flirting.

The aim of the study: in the context of parametric concept of meaning, to identify on the basis of applied psycholinguistic research the semantic components of the stimulus “flirting person”, which are actualized in the speech acts of Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine.

Material and Methods:

The main method of the research is a psycholinguistic experiment whose major stage is the controlled association experiment with the stimulus “flirting person”. The sample comprised 215 young people (aged 21-35), of which 112 females and 103 males.

Results:

At the final stage of formulation of the instructions 23 semantic features were selected for the stimulus “flirting person”. The results of the controlled association experiment with the stimulus “flirting person” allowed to build 23 associative fields and obtain the material for describing the behaviour pattern of ludic position Diplomat (flirting person) reflecting the reality of linguistic consciousness of young Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine.

Conclusions:

Cluster analysis of the associative field of the semantic feature “What is the person’s marital status?” allowed to define: three core clusters – “Free” (71.16%), “In a relationship” (14.42%), “Any” (3.72%); three peripheral clusters – “Qualities” (3.26%), “Emotional State” (3.26)%, “Role in family relations” (1.40%); extreme peripheral clusters – “Changeable” (0.93%); an isolated female reaction “Guy” suggests an ambiguous interpretation and allows to highlight different meanings – “Gender” and “Age”.

Keywords:

ludic competence, playfulness, ludic position, flirting person, psycholinguistic experiment, controlled association experiment, youth

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Introduction

This article continues a series of studies devoted to ludic competence/playfulness and one of its components is flirting (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a).

We define ludic competence as a system of inner resources to which a person turns (in the context of conflict/difficult interpersonal interaction) in order to balance their personality against external conditions of the social environment on the basis of positive emotions, interest and joy, which are frequently expressed affectively and accompanied by tension and excitement. By inner resources we understand playfulness, an integral stable personality trait.

Playfulness as a stable personality trait has been studied by the scientists since 1975 (Barnett, 1990; Bowman, 1987; Bundy, 1996; Chapman, 1978; Csikszentmihalyi, 1975; Groos, 1976; Guitard et al., 2005; Proyer, 2012; 2017; Proyer & Jehle, 2013; Qian & Yarnal, 2011; Schaefer & Greenberg, 1997; Shen, 2010; Yue et al., 2016) covering person's system of personality resources, adaptational potential, etc. and first of all it is associated in general with mental well-being; coping strategies; social intelligence and in particular with "virtual type of communicative competence" (Kobzieva, 2020, p. 38).

We determine playfulness as an integral stable personality trait, which shows as the individual creative adaptation to the reality of their own "Self" (individual identity) and to the reality of the "Other" (social identity): every conflict/difficult situation can be faced as a challenge rather than a threat. This definition of playfulness is close to the concept of Guitard et al. (2005, p. 19). From this point on the "Other" is understood as a subject/subjects of conflict/difficult interpersonal interaction.

The research of playfulness is carried out by means of psycholinguistic instruments.

The principal stage of the psycholinguistic experiment included a longitudinal free association test with the stimulus "playfulness" on the sample of 4,795 respondents that allowed to verify the components of playfulness and corresponding ludic positions: "sensitivity" (sensitive) – "Empath"; "humour" (funny) – "Real humourist"; "ease" (easy) – "balance-master"; "imagination" (imaginative) – "Sculptor"; "flirting" (flirtatious) – "Diplomat"; "impishness" (impish) – "Frolicsome fellow"; "fugue" (fugue) – "Holy fool" (Gordienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018; Kobzieva et al., 2019).

The components of playfulness/ ludic competence are defined as "self-motivated abilities" (Raven, 2001), which allow people to achieve personally significant goals. In terms of our concept such goal is efficient management of conflicts/problems in the context of interpersonal interaction (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a).

As it is shown above, each of seven "self-motivated abilities" has a corresponding ludic position. The names of ludic positions are justified both theoretically and empirically (Gordienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018; Kobzieva et al., 2019) and were tested

during coaching sessions in ludic competence, which are part of the curriculum of psychology students in H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University. Ludic position is a way how individual creative adaptation to the reality of their own "Self" and to the reality of the "Other". Ludic position reflects the experience of displaying playfulness/ludic competence in various standard and non-standard situations, i.e. a behavioral aspect. Thus, acquiring the ludic positions implies acquiring behavior patterns.

Within our research we are especially interested in the studies where a close relationship of flirting and playfulness is shown.

Playfulness is a subject of active research as a highly desirable trait in potential long-term mates (Chick et al., 2012; Fredrickson, 2003; Gordienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018; Kobzieva et al., 2019; J. Lauer & Lauer, 2002; Proyer & Wagner, 2015; Weber & Ruch, 2012) starting with the studies of Woll (1989), where playfulness is associated with different styles of sexual behavior, certain types of affection and love:

- playfulness as a spontaneous, idiosyncratic "private game" plays a definite part in establishing positive relationships and settling conflicts and, more broadly, tends to stabilize family relationship (Betcher, 1981);
- playfulness as an important trait of potential partners for romantic relationship (J. Lauer & Lauer, 2002; Fredrickson, 2003; Weber & Ruch, 2012);
- playfulness is an evolutionarily significant characteristic when choosing a sexual partner as "a highly desirable trait in long-term sexual mates" (Chick et al., 2012; Proyer & Wagner, 2015).

Certainly, we also considered the studies where flirting was the subject of research without any connection with playfulness. As a psychological phenomenon flirting and its certain aspects are covered in the works of Bern (2017) as a kind of light game, which implies presence of a double secret interaction of ego states and in the works of Gangestad (cited by Rodgers, 1999), as a negotiation process that takes place after an initial contribution. Hall (2013) identified 5 styles of flirting; Henningsen et al. (2008) determined 6 motives of flirting; Watzlawick (1983) defined 30 steps of flirting "from the first eye contact to sex"; Givens (1978, p. 346–359) and Whitty (2003, p. 343–344) described non-verbal cues for flirting.

Based on theoretical and empirical studies of the scientists mentioned above, the results of psycholinguistic studies, flirting as an individual scale of ludic competence/playfulness was singled out in the structure of ludic competence questionnaire (LCQ) developed in terms of psycholinguistics by domestic psychologists Kobzieva et al. (2019).

In the frame of our ludic competence coaching sessions we consider flirting as the ability to take attention and get on the right side of somebody of the same or the opposite gender through verbal and non-verbal communication in order to establish and maintain mutually beneficial relationships based on the feeling of emotional bond; "to promote" Other in the desired

direction (Kobzieva et al., 2019).

In our ludic competence coaching sessions describing the behaviour pattern of a ludic position rest upon its psychological and psycholinguistic structure. Identifying the specific psycholinguistic structure implies carrying out psycholinguistic experiments. The results of the psycholinguistic experiment allow to consider: gender-specific differences in the perception of the stimulus flirting, emotional and evaluative attitude to it, relevant meanings of flirting for the linguistic consciousness of the Russian-speaking population of Ukraine, etc. The psycholinguistic study of concept flirting conducted by Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., (2021a) made it possible to broaden both its meaning due to the semantic components actualized in speech acts and partly the behaviour pattern of the corresponding ludic position – Diplomat (Kobzieva et al., 2019).

We “describe” this behaviour pattern of the ludic position Diplomat in the context of parametric concept of the meaning for the first time.

Inventory of semantic features of lexemes of the language is a relevant psycholinguistic problem.

The aim of the study. In the context of parametric concept of meaning, to identify on the basis of applied psycholinguistic research the semantic components of the stimulus “flirting person”, which are actualized in the speech acts of Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine.

In accordance with the purpose the following research tasks were determined:

- to develop instructions for a controlled association experiment (CAE) based on the semantic features relevant to the semantics of “flirting person”;
- to present the main strategies and methods of distributing the obtained associates for the semantic features into the semantic clusters.

Materials and Methods

The method of the conducted research was a psycholinguistic experiment, whose main stage was the CAE with the stimulus “flirting person”. Additional methods included a survey (to clarify the results of the CAE), questionnaires (to clarify the characteristics of the sample). Frequency and cluster analysis were used as mathematical and statistical methods for analyzing the research results, which made it possible to identify trends in distribution of associations in the experimental group.

The CAE with the stimulus “flirting person” was carried out in writing. According to the instructions, the respondents should indicate gender, age, education/specialty, marital status and write the first word that comes into mind when answering each question (semantic feature).

The total number of respondents who took part in the experiment was 215 young people (age 21-35), 112 females and 103 males. “By education”: 44% – were undergraduates, 35% – had a university degree, 9% – completed secondary school; “by marital status”: 60% – were in a marriage-like relationship (unregistered

marriage), 13% – are in a registered civil marriage, 27% – are not in a relationship.

CAE allows to focus on the peripheral components and evaluativity of the stimulus word in question, while the free experiment foregrounds the brightest components of meaning. When formulating the instructions for the CAE in terms of the parametric concept of Sternin (2011), we firstly identified the main semantic features of the sense class of lexis to which our stimulus “flirting person” belongs.

The parametric concept of meaning assumes that the meaning is built from certain semantic features and different semantic types of lexis should have different set of these features. Defining the semantic features for a psycholinguistic experiment with certain semantic classes of lexis requires special research. Therefore, we used the semantics of the names of persons with semantic features described in the work of Sternin “Psycholinguistic meaning of a word and its description” (Sternin, 2011, p. 132–139), for example: the bearer of the feature, appearance, age, experience, etc.

The principal semantic parameters relevant to communication were obtained in the course of describing the meanings of Russian nouns in Sternin’s work “The lexical meaning of word in speech” (Sternin, 1985).

For the sake of convenience, all semantic features are given within the framework of the corresponding semantic aspects (for example, biological aspect, temporal aspect, social and cultural aspect, etc.). As for emic specifiers, they are given along with the corresponding semantic features if this feature is closed. If the feature is open, semantic specifiers are not given, since in this case their number is unlimited (Sternin, 2011, p. 135). For example, such a semantic aspect as biological (aspect) includes four semantic features: 1) demand for food: high, low; 2) biological state; 3) attitude to the opposite gender; 4) health: healthy, unhealthy. In the biological aspect we have selected the second and third semantic features. We give in brackets a number of a semantic feature according to Sternin’s classification (Sternin, 2011, p. 135) and a semantic feature we that have added is given with number and asterisk. The question itself is highlighted in capital letters, as it is given in the instructions; the number of the question corresponds to the number in the instruction, which is be given below.

Biological aspect:

2. What is the person’s gender? (biological gender: male, female).

13. What is the person’s attitude to the opposite gender? (attitude to the opposite gender).

14. What is the person’s attitude to the same gender? (attitude to the same gender).

Thus, depending on the semantics of a particular word, suitable semantic features are selected for posing a question and formulating the instructions.

At the initial stage the formulation procedure for the instructions for the CAE with the stimulus “flirting person” also implied systematization and generalization

of the outcomes of theoretical and empirical psychological studies devoted to the phenomenon of “flirting”; systematization and generalization of the results of psycholinguistic research devoted to the concept of “flirting”.

Results

We have formulated 28 questions (semantic features). The 28-question instructions passed approbation on a sample of 115 respondents (age 21-35). Based on the results of the analysis of the obtained associative fields, at the intermediary stage 26 questions were left. At the final stage of the study, 23 semantic features were selected; they were recognized as relevant for the stimulus flirting person and allowed to obtain the material reflecting the reality of linguistic consciousness of native speakers in order to describe the behaviour pattern of the ludic position Diplomat (flirting person). In the Table A only those questions-semantic features (first column), which reflect best the content of the behaviour pattern of the ludic position Diplomat, are given. The semantic feature numbering in the table corresponds to their numbering in our questionnaire. Semantic features did not include in Table A:

5. What is the state of the person's finances?
6. What social class does the person belong to?
9. What is the person's moral stature?
14. What is the person's attitude to the same gender?
19. What is the person's behavior?
21. What is the person's motive?
23. What is your overall assessment of the person?

In the course of building an associative field for each semantic feature, the frequencies of reactions are calculated, and the frequencies of all reactions indicated by the corresponding number are presented in descending order. If the frequencies are equal, the responses go in alphabetical order. The number of respondents who declined to answer is indicated at the end of a built associative field. The reactions (words with an asterisk) in the presented associative fields (second column) in the original research correspond to the feminine Russian words.

The outcome of the study assumes distribution of 215 reactions across semantic clusters for each of the 23 semantic features. In one of our studies, the semantic feature “What is the person's motive?” (Gordienko-Mitrofanova et al., 2021b) was considered. In this work we consider another one of 23 semantic features of the word combination “flirting person” – “What is the person's marital status?” The association reactions obtained for this semantic parameter on the sample of 215 respondents (112 women and 103 men) are as follows: 40 unique reactions, including 4-word combinations, 19 reactions with a frequency greater than one, 21 isolated reactions, 0 declined to answer the question.

215 reactions were grouped into the following clusters (semantic groups):

1. “Free”: free (50), single (28), not married (23), bachelor (17), not in a relationship (11), single* (10), actively in quest (3), none (3), widower (2), not married* (2), nobody (2), empty (2); total 153 (71.16%), of which female 73 (33.95%), male 80 (37.21%).

2. “In a relationship”: total 31 (14.42%), of which female 21 (9.77%), male 10 (4.65%).

This cluster consists of two sub-clusters:

2.1 “Registered relationship (marriage)”: married (10), married* (8); total 18 (8.37%), of which female 14 (6.51%), male 4 (1.86%).

2.2 “Unregistered relationship”: in a relationship (10), goes out with somebody (1), busy (1); at the initial stage of romantic relationships (1); total 13 (6.05%), of which female 7 (3.26%), male 6 (2.79%).

3. “Any”: any (4), it doesn't matter (4); total 8 (3.72%), of which female 5 (2.32%), male 3 (1.40%).

4. “Qualities”: kind (1), caring* (1), reliable* (1), responsible* (1), open (1), positive (1), family man (1); total 7 (3.26%), of which female 4 (1.86%), male 3 (1.40%).

5. “Emotional state”: happy (3), in love (2), beloved* (1), amorous (1); total 7 (3.26%), of which female 2 (0.93%), male 5 (2.33%).

6. “Role in family relations”: chief (1), equal (1), average (1); total 3 (1.40%), of which female 2 (0.93%), male 1 (0.47%).

7. “Changeable”: changeable (1), free (not exactly) (1); total 2 (0.93%), of which female 1 (0.47%), male 1 (0.47%).

8. “Gender”, “Age”: guy 1 (0.47%), female (0.47%).

Uninterpreted reactions are as follows:

1) reactions whose connection with the stimulus “flirting person” is individual and incomprehensible to the researchers: I don't understand (1), norm (1); total 2 (0.93%), female (0,93%);

2) echo reaction: flirting person 1 (0.47%), female (0.47%).

To make it more obvious, the clusters described above are shown in Figure 1. As can be seen from the diagram, most respondents (71.16%) believe that flirting person is free (“Free”), 14.42% suppose that he can be in a relationship (“In a relationship”), 3.72% of the respondents consider that marital status does not matter (“Any”), 0.93% admit that marital status can change (“Changeable”). Peripheral clusters (less than 10.0%, but more than 1.0%) such as “Qualities” (3.26%), “Emotional state” (3.26%) in terms of scientific philological analysis turn out to be “false” in quotation marks, since nothing is false in the psycholinguistic meaning as well as in the clusters of semantic features. There, all semantic components make the psychological reality (Sternin, 2011, p. 148). The peripheral cluster “Role in family relations” (1.40%) is contamination: it is confused with role in the family. And, finally, the isolated female reaction “guy” suggests an ambiguous interpretation and allows to highlight different meanings – “Gender” and “Age”.

Figure 1

Results of Cluster Analysis of the Semantic Feature “What is the Person’s Marital Status?”

Figure 2 also reflects gender differences in perception of the question (semantic feature) “What is the person’s marital status?”. Here the nuclear cluster (more than 10%), which we called for our purpose “In a relationship”, draws attention. This cluster is

represented mostly by female reactions (female 10%, male 5%), i. e. women admit that flirting person, regardless of gender, can be in a registered or unregistered relationship.

Figure 2

Results of Comparative Analysis of Associations of Male and Female Samples of the Semantic Feature “What is the Person’s Marital Status?”

Figure 3 shows the results of cluster analysis of the semantic feature “What is the person’s motive?” described in detail in the study “Flirting person” in the linguistic consciousness of the Russian-speaking

population of Ukraine (based on the results of the controlled association experiment) (Gordienko-Mitrofanova et al., 2021b).

Figure 3

Results of Cluster Analysis of the Semantic Feature “What is the Person’s Motive?”

Figure 4 demonstrates gender differences in perception of the question (semantic feature) “What is the person’s motive?”.

The semantic content of this semantic parameter

depends on gender identification based on the results of the analysis of female and male associative fields. Males are driven by the sexual or indefinite motives, whereas females have social and entertaining ones.

Figure 4

Results of Comparative Analysis of Associations of Male and Female Samples of the Semantic Feature “What is the person’s motive?”

Discussion

We are not aware of any studies in the Ukrainian, Russian and English languages covering the controlled association experiments with the stimulus “flirting person”. This is the basis for the fact that when describing the psycholinguistic structure of the behavior pattern of ludic position Diplomat, we can only rely on free association experiments with the stimulus “flirting” conducted by the domestic scientists (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a; Kobzieva et al., 2020) and Russian scientists (Karaulov et al., 2002), who carried out their studies in the 90s of the twentieth century. At the same time, the latter (the studies of Russian scientists) can only be used in comparative analysis of the semantic components of the word “flirt” that are relevant in speech in different time periods.

At this stage of the study, according to the results of the analysis of the built associative fields for each semantic feature of the stimulus “flirting person”, firstly, we can claim that the method we chose for formulating the instructions for the CAE based on the semantic features of the word semantics, which had been developed by Sternin (1985) in terms of the parametric concept of meaning, is the most adequate for describing behaviour patterns of the ludic positions. This is confirmed by the results of the free association experiment (FAE) with the stimulus “Holy Fool” (Gordiienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018). The results obtained are quite useful for describing the psychological and psycholinguistic structure of a behaviour pattern, but they do not allow to obtain distinctive features of the object under study. By comparison, CAE directly allows to actualize the

behavioral aspect using semantic features and semantic specifiers, for example, in the instructions these are semantic features 6-22.

Secondly, the results of clustering, for example, the semantic feature “What is the person’s motive?”, strongly indicate that the method we have chosen is the most adequate for achieving our target. For example, all six motives of flirting described by Henningsen and his colleagues in the context of theory of cognitive valence theory (sexual, relational, exploring, esteem, instrumental, and fun) (Henningsen et al., 2008) find their confirmation not only in the linguistic consciousness of Russian-speaking residents of Ukraine, but also expand the range of motives, as Figure 3 shows, through the extreme peripheral clusters – “indefinite motive” and “motive of intrinsic motivation”.

The results of clustering the semantic feature “What is the person’s marital status?” presented in this study, indirectly reflect both the empirical data of Henningsen and his colleagues and the five styles of flirting identified by Hall (physical, traditional, sincere, polite, and playful), which were confirmed by the exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses on the big sample of adults (N = 5020) (Hall et al., 2010; Hall, 2013). The clustering data of the given semantic feature are also reflected in the results of the FAE with the stimulus “flirting”, for example, in such clusters as “forms and types of interaction” (25.25%) and “gender” (10.5%) (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a).

On the one hand, the presented semantic features and semantic specifiers certainly reflect not all semantic components but only those which are most often

actualized in the acts of speech. And formulation of these components has a relative nature since all the components of meaning have more than a single description in the metalanguage, and metalanguage variants of description of the same component can take place (Sternin, 2011, p. 139). On the other hand, through formulating the instructions for CAE by means of semantic features with the stimulus “flirting person” we can obtain a large number of associations reflecting various differential features of the object under study.

Conclusions

This study belongs to a number of scientific works devoted to the analysis and description of the concepts of culture and national linguistic pictures of the world. We see the prospect of further research in clustering semantic features defined for the stimulus “flirting person”. This will make it possible to describe the psychological and psycholinguistic structure of the ludic position Diplomat corresponding to such a “self-motivated ability” of playfulness/ludic competence as flirting as a unit of psychological reality of linguistic consciousness of young Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine by means of attraction of a large number of peripheral semantic meanings, as well as semantic components of a linguistic and cultural nature, which cannot be detected by traditional methods of semantic analysis.

Ethical Approval

The authors ensure that the study has been carried out in accordance with The Code of Ethics of the World Medical Association (Declaration of Helsinki) for experiments involving humans; approved by the local institutional review board (protocol No. 12 of the Department of Psychology of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, 22.03.2021). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

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References

- Barnett, L. A. (1990). Playfulness: definition, design, and measurement. *Play and Culture*, 3, 319–336
- Betcher, R. W. (1981). Intimate play and marital adaptation. *Psychiatry*, 44(1), 13–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00332747.1981.11024088>
- Bern, E. (2017). *Igryi, v kotoryie igrayut lyudi: Psihologiya chelovecheskih vzaimootnosheniy. Lyudi, kotoryie igrayut v igryi: Psihologiya chelovecheskoy sudbyi [Games people play: The Psychology of human relationships. People who play games: The Psychology of human destiny]*. FAIR–PRESS [in Russian].
- Bowman, J. R. (1987). Making work play. In G. A. Fine (Ed.), *Meaningful play, playful meanings* (pp. 61–71). Human Kinetics.
- Bundy, A. C. (1996). Play and playfulness: What to look for. In D. L. Parham & L. S. Fazio (Eds.), *Play*

- in occupational therapy for children* (pp. 52–66). Mosby.
- Chapman, J. A. (1978). Playfulness and the development of divergent thinking abilities. *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 4(6), 371–383. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2214.1978.tb00096.x>
- Chick, G., Yarnal, C., & Purrington, A. (2012). Play and mate preference: Testing the signal theory of adult playfulness. *American Journal of Play*, 4(4), 407–440.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1975). Play and intrinsic rewards. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 15(3), 41–63. <http://doi.org/10.1177/002216787501500306>
- Fredrickson, B. L. (2003). The value of positive emotions. *American Scientist*, 91(4), 330–335. <https://doi.org/10.1511/2003.4.330>
- Givens, D. B. (1978). The nonverbal basis of attraction: Flirtation, courtship, and seduction. *Interpersonal and Biological Processes*, 41(4), 346–359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00332747.1978.11023994>
- Gordienko-Mytrofanova, I., & Kobzieva, Iu. (2018). Concept “Holy Fool” in the linguistic world-image of the Russian-speaking population of Ukraine. *Psycholinguistics*, 24(1), 10–24. <https://doi.org/10.31470/2309-1797-2018-24-1-118-133>
- Gordienko-Mytrofanova, I., Kobzieva, I., & Hohol, D. (2021a). Investigating the concept of “Flirting” as reflected in the Russian-speaking Ukrainians’ linguistic consciousness. *Psycholinguistics*, 29(1), 8–29. <https://doi.org/10.31470/2309-1797-2021-29-1-8-29>
- Gordienko-Mitrofanova, I. V., Sauta, S. L., Bezkorovainy, S. P., Konok, M. O., & Hohol, D. M. (2021b). “Liudyna, yaka flirtuie” v movnii svidomosti rosiiskomovnoho naseleennia Ukrainy (za rezultatamy spriamovanoho asotsiatyvnoho eksperymentu) [“Flirting person” in the linguistic consciousness of the Russian-speaking population of Ukraine (based on the results of the controlled associative experiment)] [Manuscript submitted for publication]. *International Journal of Education and Science*, 4(2). [in Ukrainian]
- Groos, K. (1976). The play of man: Teasing and love-play. In J. Brunner, A. Jolly, & K. Sylva (Eds.), *Play, development and evolution* (pp. 62–83). Penguin Books.
- Guitard, P., Ferland, F., & Dutil, É. (2005). Toward a better understanding of playfulness in adults. *OTJR: Occupation, Participation and Health*, 25(1), 9–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/153944920502500103>
- Hall, J. A. (2013). *The five flirting styles: Use the science of flirting to attract the love you really want*. Harlequin.

- Hall, J., Carter, S., Cody, M. J., & Albright, J. M. (2010). Individual differences in the communication of romantic interest: Development of the flirting styles inventory. *Communication Quarterly*, 5(4), 365–393. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01463373.2010.524874>
- Henningsen, D. D., Braz, M., & Davies, E. (2008). Why do we flirt? Flirting motivations and sex differences in working and social contexts. *The Journal of Business Communication*, 45(4), 483–502. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021943608319390>
- Karaulov, Yu. N., Cherkasova, G. A., Ufimtseva, N. V., Sorokin, Yu. A., & Tarasov, Ye. F. (2002). *Russkiy assotsiativnyy slovar [Russian associative dictionary]*. Astrel. [in Russian]
- Kobzieva, Iu., Gordiienko-Mytrofanova, I., Udovenko, M., & Sauta, S. (2020). Concept “Humour” in the linguistic consciousness of the Russian-speaking population of Ukraine. *European Journal of Humour Research*, 8(1), 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.7592/EJHR2020.8.1.kobzieva>
- Kobzieva, I., Gordiienko-Mytrofanova, I., Zuiev, I., & Sauta, S. (2019). Razrabotka oprosnika igrovoy kompetentnosti (OIK) [Development of ludic competence questionnaire (LCQ)]. *Psychological Journal*, 5(12), 280–301. <https://doi.org/10.31108/1.2019.5.12.19> [in Russian]
- Kobzieva, Yu. A. (2020). *Psykholohichni ta psykholinhvistychni osoblyvosti rozvytku humoru yak komponenta ihrovoi kompetentnosti [Psychological and psycholinguistic features of the development of humor as a component of ludic competence]* [Doctoral dissertation]. Hryhorii Skovoroda University in Pereiaslav. <https://ephshair.phdpdpu.edu.ua/handle/89898989/89/5243?show=full> [in Ukrainian]
- Lauer, J. C., & Lauer, R. H. (2002). *The play solution: How to put the fun and excitement back into your relationship*. McGraw-Hill.
- Proyer, R. T. (2017). A new structural model for the study of adult playfulness: Assessment and exploration of an understudied individual differences variable. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 108, 113–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.12.011>
- Proyer, R. T. (2012). Examining playfulness in adults: Testing it’s correlates with personality, positive psychological functioning, goal aspirations, and multi-methodically assessed ingenuity. *Psychological Test and Assessment Modeling*, 54(2), 103–127.
- Proyer, R. T., & Jehle, N. (2013). The basic components of adult playfulness and their relation with personality: The hierarchical factor structure of seventeen instruments. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 55(7), 811–816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2013.07.010>
- Proyer, R. T., & Wagner, L. (2015). Playfulness in adults revisited: The signal theory in German speakers. *American Journal of Play*, 7(2), 201–227.
- Qian, X. L., & Yarnal, C. (2011). The role of playfulness in the leisure stress-coping process among emerging adults: an SEM analysis. *Leisure/Loisir*, 35(2), 191–209. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14927713.2011.578398>
- Raven, J. (2001). *The conceptualisation of competence*. Peter Lang Publishing, Inc.
- Rodgers, J. E. (1999, January 1). Flirting fascination. *Psychology Today*. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/articles/199901/flirting-fascination>
- Schaefer, C., & Greenberg, R. (1997). Measurement of playfulness: A neglected therapist variable. *International Journal of Play Therapy*, 6(2), 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0089406>
- Shen, X. (2010). *Adult playfulness as a personality trait: Its conceptualization, measurement, and relationship to psychological well-being* [Doctoral dissertation]. The Pennsylvania State University. <https://etda.libraries.psu.edu/catalog/11579>
- Sternin, I. A. (1985). *Leksicheskoye znachenije slova v rechi [The lexical meaning of word in speech]*. Lambert. [in Russian]
- Sternin, I. A. (2011). *Psiholingvisticheskoe znachenie slova i ego opisanie [Psycholinguistic meaning of the word and its description]*. Lambert. [in Russian]
- Watzlawick, P. (1993). *The situation is hopeless, but not serious (The pursuit of unhappiness)*. Revised ed. W. W. Norton & Company. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1545-5300.1984.121_8.x
- Weber, M., & Ruch, W. (2012). The role of character strengths in adolescent romantic relationships: An initial study on partner selection and mates’ life satisfaction. *Journal of Adolescence*, 35, 1537–1546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.06.002>
- Whitty, M. Th. (2003). Cyber-flirting: playing at love on the Internet. *Theory & Psychology*, 13(3), 339–357. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959354303013003003>
- Woll, S. B. (1989). Personality and relationship correlates of loving styles. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 23(4), 480–505. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-6566\(89\)90016-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-6566(89)90016-0)
- Yue, X. D., Leung, C. L., & Hiranandani, N. A. (2016). Adult playfulness, humor styles, and subjective happiness. *Psychological Reports*, 119(3), 630–640. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033294116662842>

Table A

Semantic Features for the Stimulus “Flirting Person” and Corresponding Associative Fields

Questions (semantic features)	Associative fields (frequencies of reactions)
1. Who is the person as a carrier of the feature?	Girl (33), person (30), man (26), he (18), guy (17), woman (14), she (13), friend (3), Kirill (3), Casanova (2), coquetry (2), flirtatious person (2), interested person (2), playful (2), Alina Derkach (1), Anton (1), anyone (1), attractive (1), carefree (1), Dima (1), dude (1), everybody (1), explorer (1), female hobgoblin (1), fox (1), fellow student (1), female (1), flirting addict (1), flirt-bearer (1), groupmate* (1), girl with low moral standards (1), girlfriend (1), handsome man (1), hare (1), husband (1), I don't know (1), in love (1), intellectual (1), interesting* (1), interlocutor (1), lion (1), me (1), makes a good impression (1), mademoiselle (1), player (1); party girl (1), pickup artist (1), raccoon (1), she mispronounces “r” or she does it properly (1), seducer (1), swear word (1), tom-cat (1), tempter (1); timid person (1), turtle (1), vamp (1), Vasya (1), wave (1), walking (1), who (1), words (1).
2. What is the person's gender?	Female (104), male (92), doesn't matter (5), wooden (5), any (2), he (2), laminate (2), girl (1), red (1), transgender (1).
3. What is the person's age?	Twenty (33), twenty five (28), twenty three (13), middle (13), young (13), twenty one (8), twenty four (8), eighteen (7), any (6), from twenty to thirty (5), nineteen (4), twenty two (4), doesn't matter (3), from twenty to twenty five (3), sixteen (3), thirty (3), young (3), from eighteen to twenty two (2), from eighteen to thirty (2), from nineteen to twenty five (2), from seventeen to twenty five (2), of age (2), sufficient (2), twenty eight (2), twenty six (2), adult (1), agemate (1), big (1), Balzac's (1), close (1), doesn't matter* (1), from eighteen to twenty (1), from eighteen to twenty one (1), from eighteen to twenty three (1), from eighteen to thirty one (1), from twenty to twenty two (1), from twenty to forty five (1), from twenty to thirty five (1), from twenty one to thirty (1), from twenty five to twenty eight (1), from twenty five to thirty (1), from twenty four to twenty eight (1), from twenty six to thirty one (1), from nineteen to twenty six (1), female (1), from sixteen to twenty six (1), from fifteen to one hundred (1), from fifteen to sixty (1), twenty and up (1), from seventeen to twenty eight (1), forty (1), forty five (1), he (1), junior (1), mature (1), normal (1), older (1), summer (1), small (1), seventeen (1), twenty seven or twenty eight (1), twenty and older in the spring of life (1), thirty two (1), thirty years old (1), thirty five (1), young (1), young - about 20 human years old (1).
4. What is the person's marital status?	Free (50), single (28), not married (23), bachelor (17), not in a relationship (11), in a relationship (10), married (10), single* (10), married* (8), doesn't matter (4), of any status (4), actively in quest (3), happy (3), none (3), empty (2), in love (2), not married* (2), nobody (2), widower (2), amorous (1), average (1), a family man (1), at the initial stage of a romantic relationship (1), beloved* (1), busy (1), caring* (1), changeable (1), chief (1), equal (1), free (not sure) (1), goes out with somebody (1), guy (1), I don't understand (1), kind (1), normal (1), open (1), person who flirts (1), positive (1), responsible* (1), reliable* (1).
7. How intelligent is the person?	Smart (56), high (28), average (27), educated (13), developed (11), above average (8), intellectually savvy (7), erudite (5), any (3), dumb (3), pretty clever (3), quick-witted (3), witty (3), well-read (3), below average (2), clever (2), genius (2), highly intelligent (2), intelligent* (2), narrow-minded (2), not stupid (2), stupid (2), adequate (1), adult (1), animated* (1), boring (1); cunning person (1), doesn't matter (1), free (1), gifted (1), I think there may be variation (1), independent (1), like me but smarter (1), mediocre (1), not very smart (1), normal (1), on a level (1), peculiar (1), personality (1), quick-witted* (1), rational (1), rocky (1); smart enough* (1), sensible (1), to some extent (1), versatile (1), weak (1), wise* (1).
8. How cultured is the person?	Cultured (48), well-conducted (28), educated (26), high (20), middle (13), high level of culture (7), developed (3), polite (3), high culture (3), adequate (2), any (2), common (2), highly cultured (2), intelligent (2), low (2), narrow-minded (2), normal (2), pleasant (2), smart (2), vulgar (2), aristocrat* (1), beautiful (1), creative* (1), confident (1), considerate (1), clinging (1), courteous (1), dependent person (1), diplomatic (1), excellent (1), enlightened (1), erudite (1), good (1), grey* (1), I don't know how to answer (1), in love (1), intellectual (1), illuminated (1), interested* (1), lowbrow (1), literate (1), liberated (1), lacking culture (1), miscellaneous (1), nontypical (1), necessarily cultured (1), not lowbrow (1), peculiar (1), person who flirts (1), posh (1), small (1), spiritual* (1), secretive (1), Slav (1), swear word (1), tolerant (1), uncultured (1), uncivilized* (1), understanding* (1), various (1), well-conducted and educated (1), well-read (1).
10. What are the person's emotions?	Emotional (30), cheerful (18), quick-tempered (14), restrained (14), stable (8), kind (7), open (6), calm (6), sincere (6), with an average level of emotions* (6), expressive (5), balanced (4), explosive* (4), impulsive (4), bright (3), liberated (3), unemotional (3), extrovert (2), energetic* (2), high (2), moderate* (2), persistent (2), passionate* (2), quiet* (2), romantic (2), self-confident (2), secretive (2), adaptive* (1), animate (1), animate* (1), any* (1), abrupt* (1), big (1), benevolent* (1), benevolent* (1), best (1), cool (1), controlled (1), crafty (1), confident (1), charismatic (1), cunning* (1), developed (1), enthusiastic (1), exuberant (1), empathic (1), frivolous (1), gentle (1), hard (1), high (1), high-quality (1), irritable (1), I don't know (1), intriguer (1), joyful (1), mature (1), multifaceted (1), not emotional (1), nothing occurs to me (1), optimist (1), open* (1), patient (1), persistent* (1), passionate (1), receptive (1), real (1), restless (1), strong-

<p>11. What is the person's appearance?</p>	<p>willed (1), sentimental (1), strong (1), sensual (1), sensitive (1), temperamental (1), unusual (1), unrestrained* (1), unrestrained (1), unbalanced (1), various (1), vulnerable (1), withdrawn* (1), wise (1). Attractive (55), beautiful* (40), pretty (20), enticing (11), pleasant* (10), sexy* (7), comely (5), cute* (3), charming (3), average* (2), brunette (2), bright* (2), interesting* (2), ordinary* (2), provocative* (2), unusual* (2), awesome* (1), any* (1), awkward (1), blonde* (1), bearded (1), brutal (1), beautiful (for me)* (1), cool* (1), childish face (1), crazy* (1), confident (1), charismatic* (1), common* (1), doesn't matter (1), deceitful* (1), extravagant* (1), European-looking girl (1), fashionable* (1), Italian* (1), juicy* (1), masculine type* (1), manly (1), manly* (1), on the make (1), mind-blowing* (1), normal (1), normal* (1), neat (1), outward* (1), pink* (1), quiet* (1), repulsive* (1), redhead* (1), skinny stature, low stature* (1), snobbish (1), splendid* (1), stunning* (1), standard* (1), strict (1), sexy (1), such (1), sophisticated* (1), swear word (1), swear word* (1), ugly* (1), which fits my human factors, life position, character* (1), well-groomed (1).</p>
<p>12. What is the person's self-esteem?</p>	<p>High (40), self-confident (29), adequate self-esteem (20), average (13), heightened self-esteem (11), normal self-esteem (11), self-confident (9), narcissistic (8), adequate (6), low (4), moderate (3), self-critical (3), self-respecting (3), unconfident (3), above average (2), honest (2), sufficient (2), perplexed (2), underappreciated (2), aggressive (1), arrogant (1), appreciated (1), balanced (1), bottom (1), confident enough (1), considerable self-esteem (1), critical (1), common (1), confident user (1), deflated (1), developed (1), different (1), hill (1), heightened (1), healthy (1), hesitation (1), inadequate (1), knows place (1), measured (1), meh (1), narcissist (1), not vain (1), not very critical (1), none (1), open (1), objective (1), puzzled (1), poor self-esteem (1), restrained (1), realistic (1), sometimes overstated self-esteem (1), self-accepting (1), sensible (1), self-sufficient (1), self-critical (1), stunning, stable (1), self-respecting (1), stable (1), unconfident (1), without feeling of his/ her own importance (1), weaselly (1).</p>
<p>13. What is the person's attitude to the opposite gender?</p>	<p>Interested (19), attentive (17), respectful (10), friendly (9), normal (8), playful (7), open (6), interesting (4), polite (4), reserved (4), tolerant (3), active (2), arrogant* (2), attractive (2), caring (2), courteous (2), cautious (2), calm (2), excellent (2), gentle (2), indifferent (2), interesting (2), kind (2), moderate (2), neutral (2), neat (2), ordinary (2), positive (2), pleasant (2), sociable (2), sympathetic (2), self-confident (2), adequate (1), accepting (1), arrogant (1), affectionate (1), assertive (1), approving (1), agreeable (1), balanced (1), charismatic (1), cunning (1), cold (1), curious (1), charming (1), courteous (1), courteous* (1), considers men to be different people and tries to build mutually beneficial relationships (1), does not often tell all the information (1), dismissive (1), does not give reasons to be jealous (1), disrespectful (1), direct (1), different (1), extroverted (1), easy to get on with (1), exciting (1), evaluating (1), flirting (1), friendly (1), friendly* (1), flirty (1), fiery (1), fair (1), free (1), gentle (1), gallant (1), good (1), gay (1), honest (1), it does not matter because I'm keen on my gender (1), interested (1), impressive (1), intimate (1), indulgent (1), knowing when to stop loving (1), loves (1), loyal (1), lickerous (1), manipulative (1), mysterious (1), not aggressive (1), not withdrawn (1), neutral (1), neutral* (1), none (1), observant (1), ordinary (1), practical (1), pleasant (1), passionate (1), persistent (1), responsive (1), resourceful (1), responsible (1), romantic (1), sweet (1), sociable (1), sharply negative (1), sexy (1), sexy* (1), seductive (1), supportive (1), tasty (1), tall (1), tries to please and entice away (1), uncompliant (1), unpredictable (1), unscrupulous (1), user (1), very partial to it (1), value (1), well-mannered (1), "??"(1).</p>
<p>15. Where does the person flirt?</p>	<p>Everywhere (46), in communication (15), not in public places (13), at home (13), in the street (10), in a bar (9), at work (8), in the company (7), at a club (6), in public places (5), in life (4), intimately (4), in underground (4), in social networks (4), in a café (4), in private (4), at a party (3), in ripe situations (3), in a public place (3), on vacation (3), where there is an opportunity (3), when meeting (3), at any time (2), in establishments (2), in any situation (2), in the behavior (2), in relations (2), with the husband (2), where it is appropriate (2), at places to meet (1), at the right time (1), at university (1), at holidays (1), at a festival (1), environment (1), in interaction (1), in actions (1), it does not matter (1), in the jungle (1), in a comfortable (1), in personal communication (1), in St. Petersburg (1), in everyday life (1), indoors (1), in conversation (1), in a restaurant (1), in transport (1), in secluded places (1), on the internet (1), on occasion (1), surrounded by (1), where the person is comfortable (1), when dancing (1), where it is profitable (1), where there is a response (1), where the person considers it to be appropriate (1).</p>
<p>16. Whom does the person flirt with?</p>	<p>With me (57), with girls (28), with everybody (16), with opposite gender (15), with a guy (13), with a man (7), with a sympathizer (7), with women (6), with a person (6), with someone who the person likes (5), with men (3), not with me (2), with a friend (2), with people (2), with him (2), with the other half (2), with the surrounding people (2), acquainted (1), doesn't show it (1), in all cases (1), in the street (1), I don't know (1), not yet (1), only with me (1), polygamous (1), when the person wants it (1), with classmates (1), with a prey (1), with female (1), with a feminine Italian (1), with a woman (1), with animals (1), with anybody the person wants (1), with coworkers (1), with lionesses (1), with a golden youth (1), with a husband (1), with male (1), with a boss (1), with her (1), with an ugly girl (1), with an object of adoration (1), with all girls (1), with acquaintances (1), with spectators (1), with many people (1), with a partner (1), with a potential partner (1), with attractive people (1), with a girlfriend (1), with a dog (1), with an interlocutor (1), with those who the person chooses (1), with those who he/ she like (1), with someone who is interesting (1), with successful people (1), with franklins (1), with a closet (1).</p>

17. How polite is the person?	Polite (78), average (21), very polite (13), well-mannered (7), averagely polite (5), gallant (4), tactful (4), tall (4), courteous (3), cultured (3), moderate (3), normal (3), polite enough (3), cad (2), gentleman (2), important (2), lovely (2), ordinary (2), adequate courtesy (1), attentive (1), above average (1), a little rough at times (1), affectionate (1), according to the situation (1), a little coarse (1), average (1), balanced (1), between a canned meat opener and a spaniel puppy (1), courteous by the circumstances (1), comfortable (1), cultured (1), common (1), charming (1), candid but well-mannered (1), delicate (1), decent (1), dignified (1), enough (1), extraordinary (1), extremely polite (1), fair (1), gentle (1), good (1), immoral (1), inconsiderate (1), insolent (1), impolite (1), moderately polite (1), maximum polite (1), not always polite (1), not very (1), not so good (1), normal (1), polite enough (1), pleasant (1), respectful (1), reserved (1), rude (1), smarmy (1), situational (1), strange (1), supportive (1), tolerable (1), tolerant (1), thoughtful (1), uncivil (1), 8 out of 10 (1), 9 out of 10 (1), 7 out of 10 (1), 4 out of 10 (1), 4 out of 5 (1), 6 out of 10 (1).
18. What is the person in showing sense of humor?	Funny (47), cheerful (31), witty (15), humorist (13), very funny (7), active (3), moderate (3), ridiculous (3), adequate (2), black (2), cheap (2), good joke (2), good sense of humor (2), likes joking (2), tall (2), playful (2), resourceful (2), sharp on the tongue (2), subtle sense of humor (2), sarcastic (2), 10 out of 10 (2), absurd (1), artistic (1), affiliate (1), angry (1), at haphazard (1), almost a comedian (1), a strange sense of humor (1), accepts jokes (1), clear (1), clown (1), candid (1), careful (1), charismatic (1), cruel (1), doesn't understand toilet humor (1), does not show (1), developed (1), delicate (1), erudite (1), easy-going (1), extraordinary (1), gallows humor (1), gloomy (1), great (1), good (1), good level of humor (1), honest (1), it would be good if my jokes truly amused her (1), it's delivered on time (1), intellectual (1), interesting (1), interesting* (1), in different ways (1), is sarcastic (1), Jim Carrie (1), masked (1), maximum (1), maximum openness (1), not decisive (1), not funny (1), no matter (1), neutral (1), nervous (1), none (1), Nurlan Saburov (1), non-funny (1), out of control (1), peculiar (1), positive (1), playful (1), sarcasm and sharpness of mind (1), sarcastic (1), satirical (1), sensible (1), severe (1), specific humor (1), stand-up subtle (1), smiling (1), sparkling (1), the soul of the company (1), too cheerful (1), teasing men or flirting (1), takes the initiative (1), veiled sharp (1), vulgar (1), with a sense of humor (1), weak (1).
20. What is the person in the expression of sexuality?	Sexy (45), passionate (27), active (12), hot (7), relaxed (7), open (6), gentle (5), reserved (5), assertive (4), attractive (4), candid (4), ordinary (4), very much (4), aggressive (3), sincere (3), with a fight (3), brutal (2), coarse (2), confident (2), desirable (2), exciting (2), flexible (2), irritating (2), persistent (2), smutty (2), absolute (1), asexual (1), attentive (1), amorous (1), average (1), awesome (1), beast (1), confused (1), charming (1), courageous (1), charismatic (1), calm (1), conscious (1), dominant (1), delicious (1), diverse (1), doesn't show any feelings yet (1), does not show much (1), direct (1), everyone wants her (1), excellent (1), experienced (1), free experimenter (1), experimenter (1), has an appetite (1), impulsive (1), I don't know (1), intrusive (1), juicy peach (1), like that (1), masculine (1), none (1), normal (1), not sexy (1), out of control (1), outgoing (1), playful (1), patient (1), passive (1), quivering (1), quick-shot (1), real (1), restless (1), smooth (1), slutty (1), sexy kitten (1), seductive (1), sensual (1), sensual* (1), sensitive (1), selfish (1), without abuse (1), worthy (1), wild (1).
22. What is the person in conflict?	Aggressive (19), calm (19), I'm trying to settle the conflict (14), reserved (10), non-conflict (8), quick-tempered (7), avoids it (4), honest (4), insistent (4), keeps silent (4), non-aggressive (4), adequate (3), defends the point of view (3), fights (3), gets angry (3), hysterics (3), jokes (3), stubborn (3), talks (3), tries to escape from conflict (3), a compromise (2), abrupt (2), bold (2), compromise (2), cunning (2), direct (2), flexible (2), interested in resolving the conflict (2), passive (2), quarrels (2), reasonably proves point or agrees that she was wrong (2), realistic (2), sincere (2), sincere* (2), soft (2), sensible (2), solves peacefully (2), smart (2), sufferer (2), violent (2), active (1), attentive (1), avoids (1), avoiding (1), attracts attention (1), adjusts others (1), but does not press (1), argues (1), bullish (1), causes the right reaction (1), constructive (1), courteous (1), doesn't throw plates (1), drinks (1), decisive (1), demonstrative (1), diplomatic (1), gets into a fight (1), goes all the way (1), goes to reconciliation (1), gives way (1), interesting (1), loves to bring to the forest (1), lies (1), loud (1), listens to the opponent without interrupting (1), then expresses the point of view (1), listener (1), not tough (1), objective (1), polite (1), proves point (1), plays (1), puts himself/ herself above others (1), quite argumentative (1), rides out (1), retreats (1), rough edges (1), rational (1), scolds (1), smooths (1), scandalous (1), settles by diplomacy (1), sensitive (1), tries not to be in the spotlight (1), tries to resolve the conflict peacefully (1), tolerant (1), warring (1), worthy (1), wise (1), watches (1).

Note. Words with an asterisk (groupmate*, interesting*, etc.) in the presented associative fields in the original research correspond to the feminine Russian words.

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SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES

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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Psychological Well-Being of COVID Positive Patients During Quarantine in a South Indian Private Hospital

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has led to unparalleled hazards to mental health globally. Many countries around the world have introduced quarantine measures. Quarantine has changed not only the plans of most people, but also their way of life. The greatest impact of quarantine is experienced by COVID positive patients who are isolated in a hospital. The aim of the study: to explore psychological well-being of COVID positive patients during quarantine in a private hospital.

Material and Methods:

In this study, 100 patients who were COVID positive were requested to fill the Quality of Life Questionnaire. A pre-validated questionnaire was used to assess the depression score amongst COVID positive patients. The analysis of the answers and respondent opinions was conducted using the Pearson method, which produced statistically relevant results.

Results:

The studied aspects of mental health patients: sleep, appetite, crying spells; happiness and hope for the future; ability to concentrate and focus and getting disturbed easily by trivia; support received from family and friends; overall outlook of life and ability to stay happy in solitude. As a result, qualitative indicators of the patients' mental health during quarantine in a private hospital were obtained.

Conclusions:

The data obtained showed that patients managed to stay happy and eat well but they talked less, had disturbed sleep and did not look forward towards a hopeful future. Some were able to shake away the blues with family, friends on Online Media but some got depressed and got crying spells and thought that their life was a failure. The study concluded that patients on quarantine were often depressed. Many patients might benefit if psychological counselling and support are employed during quarantine measures.

Keywords:

mental health, psychological well-being, quarantine, pandemic, COVID-19

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Introduction

In December 2019 there was a sudden rise in cases of pneumonia in Wuhan city, China which was later designated as Coronavirus disease by the World Health Organization (WHO) on February 11, 2020. This Coronavirus is identified as a novel strain of coronavirus that shares 79% of genetic similarity with SARS-CoV from the SARS outbreak 2003. On March 11, 2020, the WHO declared the outbreak a global pandemic (Anand et al., 2020). This outbreak has changed various aspects of the economy resulting in vast decline in tourism, aviation, agriculture and financial sectors of the country (Nicola et al., 2020). The consequences of this pandemic affected the physical and mental health of individuals more than the world anticipated (Brooks et al., 2020; Fiorillo & Gorwood, 2020; Hanna et al., 2018; Lima et al., 2020). Resulting COVID-19 has required many countries across the globe to implement early quarantine measures as the fundamental disease control tool. Mental disorders, such as anxiety, depression, are attributed to risk factors including loneliness, frustration, which is inevitable in the majority of the population during quarantine (Kang et al., 2020; Shigemura et al., 2020; Park, S.-C., & Park, 2020). Altruistic behavior towards self-isolation and voluntary quarantine should be encouraged after proper clarification through mass communication to minimize distress and long-term complications of imposed quarantine.

The aim of the study. To explore psychological well-being of COVID positive patients during quarantine in a private hospital.

Materials and Methods

In this study 100 patients who were COVID-19 diagnosed as positive by RTPCR, were requested to fill

the questionnaire. This study was approved by the Ethical and Research Board. Voluntary written informed consent was obtained in all cases. Permission was obtained from the Ethical Committee at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Chennai, India. A validated questionnaire was used to assess the depression score amongst COVID-19 positive patients. This study was conducted from May 2020 to September 2020.

Sample Size and Collection

A total of 100 COVID-19 positive patient in age group 18-60 years by RTPCR who underwent quarantine were requested to fill the Google questionnaire form "Psychosocial Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic" after written informed consent in local language. The participation was voluntary. A total of 68 responses were received and were obtained in the study. The pre-validated DSM 4 (ICDS) questionnaires were used to assess the depression score amongst COVID-19 positive patients and data was analyzed using automated Google pie charts and Percentages. Patients with a pre-existing psychiatric illness those who are not willing to be a part of the study were excluded from the study.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed for calculating the percentage of patient with different depression score. Automated Graphs were used to analyze the data.

The analysis of the answers and respondent opinions was conducted using the Pearson method, which produced statistically relevant results.

Results

Questionnaires were sent to 100 patients out of whom 68 responded. The summary results of the respondents' answers according to the developed questionnaire are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Summary Results of Respondents' Answers According to the Developed Questionnaire

Queries for participants	Distribution of the participants number according to the responses (people/%)				
	A	B	C	D	Total
1. I was bothered by things that really don't bother me	31/47.0	19/28.8	7/10.6	9/13.6	66/100.0
2. I could not get going	29/44.6	24/36.9	6/9.3	6/9.2	65/100.0
3. I felt like people dislike me	43/65.2	16/24.2	3/4.5	4/6.1	66/100.0
4. I felt sad	28/41.8	19/28.4	12/17.9	8/11.9	67/100.0
5. I had crying spells	48/73.8	10/15.4	6/9.2	1/1.6	65/100.0
6. I enjoyed life	11/16.6	7/10.6	10/15.2	38/57.6	66/100.0
7. People were unfriendly	42/63.6	19/28.8	4/6.5	1/1.1	66/100.0
8. I felt lonely	31/46.3	20/29.9	7/10.4	9/13.4	67/100.0
9. I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing	31/47.0	21/31.8	5/7.6	9/13.6	66/100.0
10. I did not feel like eating; my appetite was poor	34/51.5	17/25.8	7/10.6	8/12.1	66/100.0
11. I felt that I could not shake off the blues with the help from my family or friends	47/71.2	13/19.7	3/4.2	3/4.9	66/100.0
12. I felt I was just as good as other people	3/4.4	5/7.3	4/5.9	56/82.4	68/100.0
13. I felt that everything I did was an effort	20/30.3	11/16.6	5/7.6	30/45.5	66/100.0
14. I talked less than usual	28/41.8	15/22.4	7/10.4	17/25.4	67/100.0
15. I was happy	11/16.7	4/6.0	7/10.6	44/66.7	66/100.0
16. My sleep was restless	25/37.3	23/34.3	11/16.5	8/11.9	67/100.0
17. I felt fearful	38/56.7	15/22.4	6/9.0	8/11.9	67/100.0
18. I thought my life had been a failure	52/78.8	5/6.9	4/6.7	5/7.6	66/100.0
19. I felt hopeful about the future	6/8.8	10/14.7	8/11.8	44/64.7	68/100.0
20. I felt depressed	49/73.1	5/7.5	4/6.0	9/13.4	67/100.0

Figures 1 to 20 show the graphical representation of number of patients with different dimensions of mental health. The aspects of sleep, appetite, crying spells were recorded. The dimensions of happiness and hope for the future were analyzed. Ability to concentrate and focus and getting disturbed easily by trivia was also studied. The support received from family and friends was documented. Overall outlook of life and ability to stay happy in solitude was assessed.

According to Figure 1 a total of 47.0% respondents rarely felt that they were bothered by the things that really don't bother them; 28.8% – sometimes felt such a state; only 13.6% respondents were bothered by the things that usually don't bother them.

Figure 1
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 1

Figure 2 shows that respondents felt as they could not get going: rarely – 44.6%, sometimes – 36.9%, occasionally – 9.3%, most of the time – 9.2%.

Figure 2
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 2

A total of 65.2% respondents felt that people rarely disliked them, only 6.1% respondents felt such a state most of the time (Figure 3).

Figure 3
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 3

The respondents answered about the sad feeling as follows (Figure 4): rarely – 41.8%, sometimes – 28.4%, occasionally – 17.9%, most of the time – 11.9%.

Figure 4
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 4

Figure 5 shows that 73.8% respondents rarely had crying spells, 15.4% – sometimes had such a state.

Figure 5
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 5

Most of the respondents (57.6%) answered to have enjoyed their life during the quarantine period, but 16.6% rarely enjoyed their life in the quarantine period (Figure 6).

Figure 6

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 6

About 63.6% respondents rarely felt that people were unfriendly to them, 28.8% of respondents felt that people sometimes were unfriendly to them (Figure 7).

Figure 7

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 7

A total of 13.4% respondents felt lonely for most of the time; 46.3% – rarely felt lonely; 29.9% – sometimes felt lonely (Figure 8).

Figure 8

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 8

A lot of people occupied themselves with other activities like WhatsApp, Twitter, Facebook and other online social media. Figure 9 shows that 13.6% respondents were unable to concentrate whatever they were doing most of the time; 47.0% respondents rarely had trouble keeping their mind on what they were doing.

Figure 9

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 9

Figure 10 shows that 51.5% respondents had a good appetite, but 12.1% respondents had poor appetite most of the time.

Figure 10

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 10

Figure 11 shows that 71.2% respondents rarely felt that they could not shake off the blues with the help from family and friends, and 19.7% respondents agreed that they were able to shake away the blues with the help of family and friends sometimes.

Figure 11
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 11

A total of 82.4% respondents felt that they were just as good as other people, but 4.4% respondents rarely felt that they were just as good as others (Figure 12).

Figure 12
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 12

Figure 13 shows that 45.5% respondents felt that everything they did was an effort most of the time, 30.3% respondents rarely felt such a state.

Figure 13
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 13

A total of 41.8% respondents rarely felt that they talked less than usual, 25.4% respondents –most of the time felt such a state (Figure 14).

Figure 14
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 14

Figure 15 shows that most of the respondents (66.7%) felt happy most of the time, but 16.7% – were unhappy.

Figure 15
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 15

According to Figure 16 37.3% respondents rarely, 34.3% respondents sometimes had restless sleep.

Figure 16
 Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 16

Figure 17 shows that 11.9% respondents felt fearful most of the time, 56.7% – rarely felt fearful.

Figure 17

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 17

Figure 20 shows that a few respondents (13.4%) actually felt depressed, while 73.1% – rarely felt depressed.

Figure 20

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 20

A total of 78.8% respondents rarely thought that their life had been a failure, but 7.6% – thought that their life had been a failure most of the time (Figure 18).

Figure 18

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 18

Figure 19 shows that 64.7% respondents most of the time were hopeful about the future, but 8.8% – rarely felt hopeful.

Figure 19

Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Query 19

Despite the fact that the study was conducted in India, its results can be useful to scientists for research on the COVID problem around the world.

Discussion

Our study explored the mental health status of the general population amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. Generally, there is a higher prevalence of symptoms of adverse psychiatric outcomes among the public when compared to the prevalence before the pandemic (Huang et al., 2019). The quarantine imposed due to the coronavirus outbreak adversely influenced people's economy because of an increase in the rate of unemployment. This led to an increased financial crisis among people and decrease in the quality of life. All these factors can put individuals at greater risk for developing adverse psychological symptoms.

Xiong et al. (2020) found that there are relatively high rates of symptoms of anxiety depression and post-traumatic stress disorders, psychological distress and stress in the general population during the COVID-19 pandemic in China. But in our study, most of the people (13.4%) felt depressed and 11.9% had sleep disturbances most of the time.

According to a study by Brooks et al. (2020), the severity of stress related symptoms will depend upon the quarantine duration and extent, the fear of being infected, feeling lonely. In our study, we found 11.6% of people felt fearful most of the time and 13.4% of people felt lonely most of the time.

According to Zhang and Ma (2020), they found a higher prevalence of insomnia, anxiety, depressive symptoms, somatization, and obsessive-compulsive symptoms in mental health staff.

A systematic review and meta-analysis (including studies from 2000 to 2014) showed an impact of an epidemic/pandemic on the mental health of health care professionals, as "probable" percentage of cases (Vyas et al., 2016). In this review, psychological distress was assessed in 13 studies, with an average rate among exposed HCPs of approximately 40% (range: 11–75%). Insomnia was assessed in four studies, with an average

rate among exposed HCPs of approximately 39% (range: 30–52%). Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms were assessed in 19 studies, with an average rate of approximately 21% (range: 10–33%), of whom 40% reported persistently high PTSD symptoms 3 years after exposure. Meta-analytic results showed effects were small, (SMD = 0.12, 95% CI = -0.23 to 0.47), but not significant. Depression symptoms were measured in 8 studies, with an average rate of approximately 46% (range: 23–74%), of whom up to 9% reported severe levels. 11% were clinically diagnosed 1 month after the disease outbreak. Meta-analytic results showed effects were moderate (SMD = 0.40, 95% CI = 0.24–0.51) and significant. Anxiety symptoms were assessed in fourteen studies. The average rate was approximately 45% (range: 19–77%). Meta-analytic results showed effects were small, (SMD = 0.08, 95% CI = -0.09 to 0.25) and not significant. In our study 67.7% of the people felt happy and 75% of the people were hopeful about the future.

One systematic review (Brooks et al., 2018) synthesizing the social and occupational factors affecting the mental health of HCPs covered the literature up to 2015 and included 22 studies, all of which had investigated the SARS epidemic. Brooks et al. (2018) identified six organizational and four social factors as showing an influence on mental health outcomes. For this rapid review, no further evidence of social and organizational factors published after 2015 was identified amongst our accepted papers. Below is a brief summary of the organizational and social factors found by Brooks et al. (2018) and associated data can be found in the study (Brooks et al., 2018). Further predictors, beyond organizational and social factors, may also influence the impact of epidemics/pandemics on mental health.

In another review it was observed that subsyndromal psychological states were common during COVID pandemic. Anxiety, depression and self-reported stress are some of the commonly reported symptoms (Rajkumar, 2020).

A study from Iran has revealed certain causes of stress and mental morbidity during COVID can be resulting from misinformation, social isolation and unpredictable nature of the disease (Zandifar & Badrfam, 2020).

Western countries have incorporated psychological interventions into their protocols for COVID outbreaks, this has not yet happened in countries such as China, India, other developing nations leading to increased prevalence of stress-related disorders in COVID affected persons. There is definitely a need for development of intervention strategies in managing COVID affected patients in hospital wards (Duan & Zhu, 2020).

Lima et al. (2020) have pointed out anxiety and depression as the most important COVID related psychological morbidity among general population and also among patients. This calls for training among health care personal for dealing COVID patients and use of technology in delivering mental care.

Resistance to post-traumatic stress reactions of vulnerable groups engaged in pandemic COVID-19 liquidation has been studied by Melnyk, Stadnik, and Pypenko (2020).

Health anxiety is the term used by some authors which is a state of mind where certain body functioning mechanisms can be misinterpreted as symptoms of infectious pandemic disease. With COVID-19 media coverage, misinformation and exaggerated information can result in excessive health anxiety not only in COVID patients but also among general population. This can result in maladaptive behaviors among masses like hoarding items, refusing treatments or making multiple visits to health care facilities etc. (Asmundson & Taylor, 2020a; 2020b).

Conclusions

The present study suggests that there is an increased stress during isolation and quarantine during pandemics. Patients manage to stay happy and eat well but they talk less, have disturbed sleep and do not look forward towards a hopeful future. Some are able to shake away the blues with family, friends on Online Media but a few do get depressed and get crying spells and think that their life is a failure. Patients often realize that the disease is difficult to cure and whatever they do is just an effort and not a cure. Many patients might benefit if psychological counselling and support are employed during quarantine measures.

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Ethical Approval

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References

- Anand, K. B., Karade, S., Sen, S., & Gupta, R. M. (2020). SARS-CoV-2: Camazotz's curse. *Medical Journal Armed Forces India*, 76(2), 136–141.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mjafi.2020.04.008>
- Asmundson, G. J. G., & Taylor, S. (2020a). Coronaphobia: Fear and the 2019-nCoV outbreak. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 70, 102196.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102196>
- Asmundson, G. J. G., & Taylor, S. (2020b). How health anxiety influences responses to viral outbreaks like COVID-19: What all decision-makers, health authorities, and health care professionals need to know. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 71, 102211.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102211>
- Brooks, S. K., Dunn, R., Amlôt, R., Rubin, G. J., & Greenberg, N. (2018). A systematic, thematic review of social and occupational factors associated with psychological outcomes in

- healthcare employees during an infectious disease outbreak. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 60(3), 248–257. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0000000000001235>
- Brooks, S. K., Webster, R. K., Smith, L. E., Woodland, L., Wessely, S., Greenberg, N., & Rubin, V. (2020). The psychological impact of quarantine and how to reduce it: Rapid review of the evidence. *The Lancet*, 395(10227), 912–920. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30460-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30460-8)
- Duan, L., & Zhu, G. (2020). Psychological interventions for people affected by the COVID-19 epidemic. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(4), 300–302. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30073-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30073-0)
- Fiorillo, A., & Gorwood, P. (2020). The consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health and implications for clinical practice. *European Psychiatry*, 63(1), E32. <https://doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2020.35>
- Hanna, F., Barbui, C., Dua, T., Lora, A., van Regteren Altena, M., & Saxena, S. (2018). Global mental health: how are we doing? *World Psychiatry*, 17(3), 367–368. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20572>
- Huang, Y., Wang, Yu., Wang, H., Liu, Z., Yu, X., Yan, J., Yu, Y., Kou, C., Xu, X., Lu, J., Wang, Z., He, S., Xu, Y., He, Y., Li, T., Guo, W., Tian, H., Xu, G., Xu, X. ... Wu, Y. (2019). Prevalence of mental disorders in China: A cross-sectional epidemiological study. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 6(3), 211–224. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(18\)30511-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(18)30511-X)
- Kang, L., Li, Y., Hu, S., Chen, M., Yang, C., Yang, B. X., Wang, Y., Hu, J., Lai, J., Ma, X., Chen, J., Guan, L., Wang, G., Ma, H., & Liu, Zh. (2020). The mental health of medical workers in Wuhan, China dealing with the 2019 novel coronavirus. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7, E14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30047-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30047-X)
- Lima, C. K. T., Carvalho, P. M. M., Lima, I. A. A. S., Nunes, J. V. A. O., Saraiva, J. S., de Souza, R. I., da Silva, C. G. L., & Neto, M. L. R. (2020). The emotional impact of Coronavirus 2019-nCoV (new Coronavirus disease). *Psychiatry Research*, 287, 112915. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112915>
- Nicola, M., Alsaifi, Z., Sohrabi, C., Kerwan, A., Al-Jabir, A., Iosifidis, C., Agha, M., & Agha, R. (2020). The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): A review. *International Journal of Surgery*, 78, 185–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijisu.2020.04.018>
- Melnyk, Yu. B., Stadnik, A. V., & Pypenko, I. S. (2020). Resistance to post-traumatic stress reactions of vulnerable groups engaged in pandemic liquidation. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 3(1), 35–44. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijsa.2020.1.5>
- Park, S.-C., & Park, Y. C. (2020). Mental health care measures in response to the 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak in Korea. *Psychiatry Investigation*, 17(2), 85–86. <https://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2020.0058>
- Rajkumar, R. P. (2020). COVID-19 and mental health: A review of the existing literature. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 52, 102066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102066>
- Shigemura, J., Ursano, R. J., Morganstein, J. C., Kurosawa, M., & Benedek, D. M. (2020). Public responses to the novel 2019 coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in Japan: Mental health consequences and target populations. *Psychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, 74(4), 281–282. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pcn.12988>
- Vyas, K. J., Delaney, E. M., Webb-Murphy, J. A., & Johnston, S. L. (2016). Psychological impact of deploying in support of the US response to Ebola: A systematic review and meta-analysis of past outbreaks. *Military Medicine*, 181(11-12), e1515–1531. <https://doi.org/10.7205/MILMED-D-15-00473>
- Xiong, J., Lipsitz, O., Nasri, F., Lui, L. M. V., Gill, H., Phan, L., Chen-Li, D., Jacobucci, M., Ho, R., Majeed, A., & McIntyre, R. S. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on mental health in the general population: A systematic review. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 277, 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.08.001>
- Zandifar, A., & Badrfam, R. (2020). Iranian mental health during the COVID-19 epidemic. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 51, 101990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.101990>
- Zhang, Y., & Ma, Z. F. (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health and quality of life among local residents in Liaoning Province, China: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(7), 2381. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072381>

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LETTER TO THE EDITOR

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A Topical Methodology Research Subject
in the European Area of Higher Education:
ELF, EFL or ESP?

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Dear Editor,

The European “ecosystem” of higher education seems to have been affected by the global pandemic in a number of ways. Some of these impacts may well be viewed as negative; some others, as giving a new impetus to the development of the entire educational system. It is evident, for instance, that the dire necessity to “go virtual” has created new avenues for the intensification of contacts between educators who previously were less motivated to do so (Magomedov et al., 2020; Melnyk et al., 2020).

That clearly manifests the fact that the ongoing process of transformations taking place in national higher education systems across Europe has not slowed down at all, which has made some of the current cultural and educational challenges even more pressing. One such challenge is the necessity to effectively use ELF (English as a lingua franca).

In recent years, the phenomenon has been covered in many publications whose authors studied it from multiple perspectives (Barančicová & Zertzová, 2015; Cogo, 2016; Jenkins, 2009). The most common approach seems to be the linguistic one, the research question being whether ELF is or isn't a qualitatively new linguistic entity.

Researchers working in post-communist countries have made valuable contributions to linguistic studies, especially in the area of EFL studies, as these countries clearly belong to the so-called Expanding Circle. However, the social and cultural realities of today call for

more focus not on EFL studies but on research in the field of ELF and ESP (English for Specific Purposes). It is explained by the fact that the ability to use ESP is now a highly desirable skill for the majority of professionals working in the post-communist part of Europe.

Traditionally, teaching EFL/ESP at tertiary level in countries like Ukraine and Belarus has been viewed as high-quality and effective. However, it mostly embraced teacher training programs that typically last four years and end in obtaining an EFL teacher certificate. In contrast, ESP programs offered to students of engineering or natural sciences seldom take more than a year and generally yield far more modest educational outcomes.

Universities across Western and Central Europe have long offered multiple courses in English. Yet higher education establishments operating today in Eastern Europe are not quite capable of following the same path. The most common reason is the lack of educational cadres who can teach their subjects using English. There are many competent English teachers but they are unable to teach courses other than those related to EFL. To do so, they need to obtain at least an additional Master's degree in the respective field (law, economics, etc.).

There is also another dimension to this problem. English is undoubtedly the language of the European academia. This brings about the need to use English throughout the entire university continuum. A specific aspect of faculty

members' activities is research, as well as subsequent publication of results. A novel academic requirement for teaching staff working at universities across Eastern Europe is the need to publish articles in English-language journals (preferably those with high impact factors). At present, however, few university teachers are able to meet such a requirement competently. Collaboration between educators working in various fields (including teaching EFL) may be viewed as a possible solution.

However, it is a short-term solution. Setting far-reaching goals requires a major shift in the theory and practice of teaching ESP, which has been pointed out repeatedly (Maslov, 2005; Maslov, 2016). It should gradually move towards a different paradigm that focuses on teaching English as a lingua franca. The logic of such an approach can help remove the contradiction between the "national" and "global" dimensions of the teaching process, which seems to be one of the perennial apples of discord in the post-Communist methodologists' community.

At present, many authors emphasize the growing need for research in the field of methodology that may take ecological and dynamic points of view (Hiver & Al-Hoorie, 2016). It means that the specifics of local contexts are supposed to receive more attention. We can witness the first signs of the growing interest in these matters. One recent example is the book by Tamilla Mammadova (2020) entitled "Exploring English Language Teaching in Post-Soviet Era Countries Perspectives from Azerbaijan". It considers the teaching of English as a lingua franca at all education levels in the countries of the former Soviet Union, with particular emphasis on universities.

We are convinced that more research in the field of ELF can definitely enrich the practices existing in East European education. It can also contribute to the global treasure house of methodology through publishing activity, as worthy educational ideas will travel east and west more freely.

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References

Barančicová, J., & Zerzová, J. (2015). English as a lingua franca used at international meetings. *JoLaCe*

Journal of Language and Cultural Education, 3(3), 30–51. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jolace-2015-0018>

- Cogo, A. (2016). English as a Lingua Franca in Europe. In A. Linn (Ed.), *Investigating English in Europe: Contexts and Agendas* (pp. 79–89). De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781614518952-014>
- Hiver, P., & Al-Hoorie, A. H. (2016). A dynamic ensemble for second language research: Putting complexity into practice. *The Modern Language Journal*, 100(4), 741–756. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12347>
- Jenkins, J. (2009). English as a Lingua Franca: interpretations and attitudes. *World Englishes*, 28(2), 200–207. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-971X.2009.01582.x>
- Magomedov, I. A., Khaliev, M.S-U., & Khubolov, S. M. (2020). The negative and positive impact of the pandemic on education. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1691, 012134. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1691/1/012134>
- Mammadova, T. (2020). *Exploring English language teaching in post-soviet era countries perspectives from Azerbaijan*. Routledge.
- Maslov, Y. V. (2005). Poetic impulse as means to produce healthier communication in English. *Prace Naukowe Akademii im. Jana Długosza w Częstochowie: Kultura Fizyczna*, 6, 201–211.
- Maslov, Y. V. (2016). Foreign-language training at tertiary level: In search for "Principled eclecticism". *Visnyk Chernihivskoho natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu – Bulletin of Chernihiv National Pedagogical University*, 141, 117–120. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/VchdpuP_2016_141_29
- Melnyk, Yu. B., Pypenko, I. S., & Maslov, Y. V. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic as a factor revolutionizing the industry of higher education. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 12(5). <https://doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v12n5.rioc1s19n2>

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LETTER TO THE EDITOR

The Play Specialist in the Pediatric Healthcare:
Evidence-Based Professionalism,
Issues in Practice, and Training
Across Different Countries

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Dear Editor,

For developmental psychologists, playing is a crucial parameter to monitor children and adolescents' physical, emotional, cognitive, and executive development and wellbeing. In the psychotherapy setting, play is a promotor of positive therapeutic change because it allows the child to express beliefs, memories, wishes, feelings, and subconscious contents, from a safe and indirect point of view. Play is a fundamental human right during the whole life cycle, and it becomes even more important for those children and adolescents who are hospitalized or experiencing medical treatments at home (European Association for Children in Hospital, 1988). Entering a medical setting can elicit children's and adolescents' distress on many levels (e.g., anxiety, depression, hypochondria, acting out, externalizing, and internalizing problems) since their familiar routine is temporarily disrupted.

In the 1920s the nurses Florence Nightingale and Florence Erikson were the first to intuit the power of play for hospitalized children: the pediatric patients who could experience play sessions with a properly trained professional were more adherent towards medical treatments (Francischinelli et al., 2012). Play can make the hospital experience enjoyable, or at least less terrifying for the youngsters. Back then, many synonyms were used to describe this role like "play-lady", "puppet lady", "play checkers", "playing teacher", and

"recreational therapist". Nowadays, there is a great terminological fragmentation in describing all the professionals trained to support children during hospitalization through age-specific and diagnosis-specific play programs. Different countries adopt different labels to describe this role, which can be defined by the keyword "Play Specialist" (Porto dei Piccoli, 2021). Play Specialist intervention differs from Play Therapy because Play Therapy is a projective technique practiced by psychotherapists in the light of a psychoanalytical framework. Play Specialist's intervention, instead, can be summarized into two core-actions (Burns-Nader & Hernandez-Reif, 2014): 1) medical play: using medical equipment and language to help the child to get used and not fear the medical setting and procedures; 2) normative play: proposing play activities to the child that are similar to play activities he or she practices at home. This establishes a sense of continuity with the life before illness, and/or offers distractions and imaginary escapes from reality. Noticeably, the Play Specialist can also offer to children with chronic conditions (e.g., diabetes or disabilities) experiential activities outside of the children's comfort-zone, to increase their health-related responsibility and self-efficacy.

The aim of the study. To foster scientific community consideration about the Play Specialist role, paying

attention to the state of the art, the international field of practice, the evidence supporting the effectiveness of the Play Specialist intervention, the main challenges, and the everyday issue that these professionals have to face to gain proper integration in the national and international healthcare system.

This contribution presents two main elements: a literature review and a small-group survey. A review of the literature (on a total of n=613 papers from Pubmed, Scopus, PsycArticles) has been conducted to describe the Play Specialist professionalism and the difficulties in the practice. Moreover, the core elements of the training across different nations in terms of the prerequisites, the duration of the training, the institutions promoting or certifying the training, and the study subjects are discussed from an inclusive perspective. Thus, data from n=9 international experts in the field are examined to describe the state of the art over the Play Specialist's training.

Literature offers a vast body of evidence supporting the Play Specialist's intervention effectiveness in fostering the hospitalized child's wellbeing.

Five key elements emerged:

1. The Play Specialist intervention improves the child's coping strategies, her/his positive emotions, and decreases anxiety and stress that may anticipate medical procedures (Gill, 2010; Ullan & Belver, 2019).
2. Children require less sedation for pain management: with the Play Specialist intervention, the child is more capable of pain management at a behavioral, physical, cognitive, and complementary level (Bandstra et al., 2008).
3. The child is more adherent to the medical treatment: since play intervention decreases negative emotions (e.g., anxiety, stress, externalizing behaviors) the child is more collaborative towards medical staff (Gill, 2010). Once achieved through medical play a major knowledge over her/his health and the healing process, the child experiences less power imbalance from the adults taking care of her/him (e.g., family members, medical staff) (Bricher, 2000).
4. Play can be crucial in palliative care: through targeted play activities the Play Specialist can help the child to face and elaborate emotions connected to end-of-life concepts (Lindqvist, 1974).
5. Time and economic savings for the hospitals: as supported by Metzger et al. (2013), the Play Specialist enhances patients' compliance, requiring less anesthesia for invasive medical procedures. This aspect is important to spare sedation costs to the hospital, and also to spare children from anesthesia and its potential collateral effects.

Literature depicts the main challenges that the Play Specialists have to face all over the world.

Five main domains emerge:

- 1) Lack of standardized methods and measures to support the practice (Goh et al., 2019) has hindered for a very long-time the possibility to create a common ground;
- 2) Practice fragmentation across different countries arise problems in the practice as the core activities are often

overlapping with other professionals' interventions like educational video gaming, pet therapy, art therapy;

3) Lack of recognition at a national and international level hinders the integration of the Play Specialist with the hospital staff (Metzger et al., 2013). Frequently, doctors and nurses may exchange Play Specialists for volunteers or may improvise play activities for their patients without having the proper training;

4) Lack of funds from national institutions represent another crucial challenge for promoting the Play Specialist as no-profit private institutions often support this professionalism (Simonelli et al., 2014);

5) Difficulties in accessing the hospitals for Play Specialist during Covid-19 waves emerged. To respond to the global crises without letting down families and children, pioneering telematic adaptations of the Play Specialist intervention have been developed (Perasso et al., 2020).

Experts offer a detailed picture of the Play Specialist formation at an international level. Data collected from the nine participants to Porto dei Piccoli's international Round Table (January 2021), reveal salient elements in the Play Specialist formation.

Across different countries, heterogeneities and commonalities emerge:

- the prerequisite of the training (e.g., a bachelor's degree in psychology or pedagogy) is required all over the world;

- the duration of the formation varies from courses of 200 hours to courses of 760 hours;

- considering the subjects of the Play Specialists' study, the countries' referents agree about offering formation on the child developmental milestones on a pediatric, psychological, pedagogical level, play-techniques, family psychology, attachment psychology;

- as regards achieving a certification at the end of the training, a few countries still struggle to obtain institutional recognition for Play Specialists and proper certification procedures. In fact, institutional certification is fundamental in providing evidence-based interventions and obtaining acknowledgment in the hospital context.

The Play Specialist's professionalism is essential to advocate children's right to play in the hospital context and to promote her/his wellbeing by fostering coping, treatment adherence, and counteracting negative emotions. Still, cross-countries differences at an educational and institutional recognition level hinder the possibility to integrate the Play Specialists in national and international healthcare systems. For the future, the exchange of best practice and research evidence among no-profit organizations, and public and private healthcare stakeholders is vividly recommended to build a common ground and finally overcome fragmentation.

References

- Bandstra, N. F., Skinner, L., Leblanc, C., Chambers, C. T., Hollon, E. C., Brennan, D., & Beaver, C. (2008). The role of child life in pediatric pain management: A survey of child life specialists. *The Journal of Pain*, 9(4), 320–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpain.2007.11.004>

- Bricher, G. (2000). Children in the hospital: Issues of power and vulnerability. *Pediatric Nursing*, 26(3), 277–282. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12026391/>
- Burns-Nader, S., & Hernandez-Reif, M. (2016). Facilitating play for hospitalized children through child life services. *Children's Health Care*, 45(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02739615.2014.948161>
- European Association for Children in Hospital. (1998). *The EACH Charter*. <https://www.each-for-sick-children.org/each-charter>
- Francischinelli, A. G. B., Almeida, F. D. A., & Fernandes, D. M. S. O. (2012). Routine use of therapeutic play in the care of hospitalized children: Nurses' perceptions. *Acta Paulista de Enfermagem*, 25(1), 18–23. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-21002012000100004>
- Gill, C. (2010). Helping children cope with renal disease: the role of play specialist. *Journal of Renal Nursing*, 2(5), 244–247. <https://doi.org/10.12968/jorn.2010.2.5.78490>
- Goh, G., Edmonds, L., & Christos, J. (2019). Development and evaluation of play specialist documentation in a New Zealand hospital. *Nursing Children and Young People*, 31(2), 32–36. <https://doi.org/10.7748/ncyp.2019.e1144>
- Lindqvist, I. (1974). Play as therapy. *Pediatrician*, 3, 295–300.
- Metzger, T., Mignogna, K., & Reilly, L. (2013). Child life specialists: Key members of the team in pediatric radiology. *Journal of Radiology Nursing*, 32(4), 153–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jradnu.2013.08.001>
- Perasso, G., Maggiore, A., Allegrì, C., & Camurati, G. (2020). Telematic intervention based on the Play Specialist approach in the COVID-19 era: Benefits for parents of children with clinical conditions. *International Journal of Preventive Health and Medicine*, 1(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijpmh.A2005.111120>
- Porto dei Piccoli. (2021, 29 January). *1st International Round Table on Playing in the Hospital*. <https://www.ilportodeipiccoli.org/it-it/round-table-e-play-specialist/>
- Simonelli, I., Raúl, M., Bennett, S., Clarke, A., Fernandes, G. A. I., Fløtten, K., Maggi, S., Robinson, J. E., Simonelli, F., Vaghri, Z., Webb, E., & Goldhagen, J. (2014). A rights and equity-based “Platform and Action Cycle” to advance child health and well being by fulfilling the rights of children. *Canadian Journal of Children's Rights*, 1(1), 199–218. <https://doi.org/10.22215/CJCR.V1I1.11>
- Ullan, A. M., & Belver, M. H. (2019). Integrative pediatrics and child care play as a source of psychological well-being for hospitalized children: Study Review. *Integrative Pediatrics and Child Care*, 2(1), 92–98. <https://doi.org/10.18314/ipcc.v2i1.1613>

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